

PREPSOIL DELIVERABLE

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Executive summary

Purpose

This deliverable, titled "D1.3 Strategy for the project's communication, dissemination, exploitation (M36)" aims to encapsulate the stakeholder engagement approach and the communication, dissemination, and exploitation (CDE) activities conducted over the 36-month duration of the PREPSOIL project, and in accordance with the three Key Impact Pathways:

- 1) Soil literacy and awareness to citizens/society at large through improved dissemination, access, and education
- 2) Improved knowledge access, exchange of experiences, training and co-creation for land managers and other stakeholders
- 3) Establishment of interaction spaces for effective mission deployment, from local to EU level contributing to fulfilling EU and international commitments thanks to input to the mission on soil needs, monitoring and living labs expertise

Audience

This deliverable offers insights for researchers, policy advisors, and civil servants involved in establishing Mirror Groups. It provides practical methods for stakeholder engagement, strategies for effective communication of scientific and project results, and a robust approach to managing exploitation activities—making it especially relevant for project coordinators.

Main activities

PREPSOIL adopted a proactive, co-creative approach to ensure alignment between project outputs and stakeholder needs. Relevant stakeholder groups for the three impact pathways were engaged through tailored strategies, drawing on partner networks, open calls, past projects, and early committed participants.

Throughout 2023, PREPSOIL collaborated with the Mission Board to clarify expectations for National Soil Hubs and Mirror Groups, aiming to identify synergies. PREPSOIL adapted to align with Mission Secretariat priorities, and the Secretariat continues to promote the development of Mirror Groups, offering examples and guidance to support their formation.

A dynamic communication, dissemination, and exploitation strategy was implemented, guided by clear KPIs—most of which were met or exceeded. Partners appointed a dedicated representative to ensure widespread, multilingual outreach.

A coordinated process gathered exploitation activities across all work packages. Using a standardised template, partners identified Key Exploitable Results (KERs) and documented actions taken to support their uptake and impact.

Key Results and their implications

Advancing Mirror Group Formation: PREPSOIL provided a clear overview of existing Mirror Group and similar national structures, helping define their purpose and the Commission's expectations. Through direct engagement with countries, practical recommendations were developed to support the creation and growth of Mirror Groups. These are now available and already sparking new initiatives across Europe.

Exceeding Expectations on Events: PREPSOIL delivered a series of impactful online and in-person events, fostering strong stakeholder engagement. Notably, the Final Event in Brussels showcased project outcomes to a broad and diverse audience.

Outstanding Exploitation Outcomes: Given the volume and quality of results, the consortium undertook a structured process to identify and document Key Exploitable Results (KERs) resulting in a consolidated set of exploitable outputs supported by targeted actions to maximise impact.

Research and practice implications

The PREPSOIL project offers valuable insights for research and practice in sustainable soil management and stakeholder engagement. Its tailored engagement strategies and support for Mirror Groups provide a practical model for aligning research with real-world needs and facilitating knowledge exchange. The identification of Key Exploitable Results (KERs) and the focus on accessible communication support the broader uptake of project outputs. These findings can guide future research, inform policy implementation, and contribute to advancing soil literacy, land management, and the EU Soil Mission's objectives.

Policy implications

The PREPSOIL findings are especially relevant for EU and national policy makers. The stakeholder engagement and communication strategies offer a model to advance soil literacy (Objective 1), knowledge exchange (Objective 2), and inclusive governance (Objective 8). Mirror Groups emerge as a practical tool for coordination and policy alignment. Policy makers should support their development and use the identified Key Exploitable Results (KERs) to inform future soil initiatives. Ongoing collaboration with the Mission Secretariat will be key to drive soil health policies forward.

Conclusion

PREPSOIL met or exceeded all major KPIs, engaging hundreds of stakeholders and delivering targeted communications through newsletters, a dynamic website, and social media channels. Strategic decisions were made throughout to maximise outreach and relevance.

This deliverable reflects the consortium's commitment to stakeholder engagement and to ensuring that outputs are needs-driven, accessible, and effectively promoted via appropriate channels and tone of voice. A substantial number of Key Exploitable Results (KERs) have been identified for uptake by future EU projects. Key outcomes—such as guidance on Mirror Groups—will remain accessible, with the website and social media channels continuing to support post-project dissemination.

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1. INTRODUCTION

WP	Task	Main Responsible	Contributing partners
WP1	T1.1	AU	TrustIT, ACTA

This deliverable, titled "D1.3 Strategy for the project's communication, dissemination, exploitation (M36)" aims to encapsulate the stakeholder engagement approach and the communication, dissemination, and exploitation (CDE) activities conducted over the 36-month duration of the PREPSOIL project, and in accordance with the three Key Impact Pathways: 1) Soil literacy and awareness to citizens/society at large through improved dissemination, access, and education; 2) Improved knowledge access, exchange of experiences, training and co-creation for land managers and other stakeholders; 3) Establishment of interaction spaces for effective mission deployment, from local to EU level contributing to fulfilling EU and international commitments thanks to input to the mission on soil needs, monitoring and living labs expertise.

It highlights the collective efforts of the consortium in engaging relevant stakeholders, to ensure that the project outputs are tailored to real needs and expectations, and in promoting these outputs thanks to easily accessible communication, in a tone of voice relevant to the stakeholder audience, and the dissemination on relevant communication channels. The document also presents a detailed overview of the Key Exploitable Results the project has produced.

On all significant KPIs (Key Performance Indicators) we have reached, if not surpassed, our targets. Hundreds of stakeholders were directly engaged as part of PREPSOIL activities, a lot of effort has been put into creating a newsletter with high quality content, always relevant to the target audience, and the website and social media channels have followed the dynamic approach from the CDE strategy. Difficult but necessary decisions have been made to ensure optimum outreach throughout the duration of the programme.

A remarkable amount of Key Exploitable Results (KERs) has been identified and prepared for further uptake by other relevant EU projects. Decisionmakers have readily offered their support, and [Impact Interviews](#) with amongst others, a member of the European Committee of the Regions, to confirm the overall contribution of PREPSOIL to improving soil health.

Looking beyond PREPSOIL, outputs like the report "Mission Soil Mirror Groups: Where do we stand? - Report", the PREPSOIL App, the Toolbox for Soil Living lab growth and the PREPSOIL Knowledge Hub will remain active and accessible. The social media channels and the website will also remain active and prepared for post project dissemination activities.

2. PREPSOIL Stakeholder Engagement: Overview

WP	Task	Main Responsible	Contributing partners
WP1	T1.2	ACTA	AU

PREPSOIL adopted a proactive approach to co-create with stakeholders. The objective was to ensure a real alignment between PREPSOIL outputs and stakeholder needs, to foster the dissemination and the future exploitation of PREPSOIL outputs among targeted stakeholders and, overall, to facilitate the empowerment of those stakeholders.

One of PREPSOIL's ultimate purposes was to generate long-lasting interaction spaces which not only require engaging with multiple stakeholders, in relation with various land uses, but also engaging with national authorities to raise their awareness and to inform them about their leverage to improve soil health.

2.1 Targeted stakeholders and purpose of engagement

WP	Task	Main Responsible	Contributing partners
WP1	T1.2	ACTA	AU

PREPSOIL approach for target audiences' segmentation for the first period (M1-M18) of the project was based on the distinction between primary stakeholders and secondary stakeholders, as described and defined in the Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication plans produced at M7 (D1.1) and M19 (D1.2) and illustrated in Figure 1.

Primary stakeholders also included living labs (LLs), national hubs, communities of practice (CoPs) and soil advocates, which were special categories that could involve a wide range of stakeholders including stakeholders otherwise identified as secondary.

Figure 1: Representation of primary and secondary Stakeholders in PREPSOIL as presented in D1.1 and D1.2.

While this approach was helpful to align our engagement activities with the project structuration in work packages and tasks, it may not clearly nor fully depict the engagement efforts done, as highlighted during the mid-term review of the project, especially as it does not illustrate how interaction with LLs, national hubs, soil advocates or communities of practice are also a way of reaching and engaging relevant stakeholders.

Therefore, for this document, in line with the observations and recommendations from the mid-term review and consistent with the actual focus of the project for the second period, our approach has been refocused on PREPSOIL's expected impact, and more specifically on ensuring that PREPSOIL would reach out to as many relevant stakeholders as possible by the end of the project, to progress along PREPSOIL's three impact pathways.

These pathways were defined to contribute to the goals and objectives of the Mission Soil:

- i. Increased soil literacy, awareness and societal appreciation
- ii. Improving the knowledge base and the access to critical information of land managers to act on soil health, including through their engagement in co-creation of best practices,
- iii. Establishment of interaction spaces for effective mission deployment, from local to EU level contributing to fulfilling EU and international commitments thanks to input to the mission on soil needs, monitoring and living labs expertise.

Figure 2 shows how the different project activities and outcomes are expected to contribute to these impact pathways.

Figure 2: Summary canvas of the project: relation between Key impact pathways and the project activities and outcomes

To progress on these pathways, PREPSOIL targeted several types of stakeholders due to their capacity to foster or put a curb on the implementation of the objectives of the Mission Soil:

- Policymakers and funding agencies at various levels, as they can affect the regulatory context at local, national or EU scale, including research priorities and form of research (co-creation)
- Land managers that use and manage directly soil resources, as well as their advisors than can also affect land managers' awareness and decision-making.
- Citizens, CSOs, NGOs and other associations, as they can affect the priorities and perceptions of decision makers (policy makers, businesses, land managers), and because society awareness of the values of soils is key to avoid soil degradation.
- Stakeholders from the private sector, that can have an impact across the entire value chain, from supplying relevant services, materials or tools, to facilitating the funding and the economic development of stakeholders and initiatives that develop, promote or mobilize sustainable soil management practices.
- Stakeholders from the education system and other awareness-raising actors, helping to educate and raise awareness of citizens and society at large, including (future) decision-makers.

- Stakeholders from the research community, as they are key to produce the knowledge needed and can affect the way co-creation with stakeholders and interactions between science – policy or science-land managers are strengthened. PREPSOIL especially targeted stakeholders involved in other projects funded under the Mission Soil.

PREPSOIL reached out to all these stakeholders through its engagement activities, its communication and dissemination actions, and its efforts to foster exploitation of PREPSOIL outputs as highlighted in section 3 and section 4.

The project also focused on specific roles (such as Soil advocates) and multi-stakeholder interfaces (such as Communities of Practices, LLs and national hubs), both to foster the development of these interfaces, as highlighted in Table 2, and as a way to reach out more stakeholders.

The various stakeholder categories identified above as relevant for our impact pathways were engaged as part of PREPSOIL activities, with a specific purpose tailored for each stakeholder category as presented in Table 1.

Stakeholder categories	Target stakeholders	Objectives for their engagement
Policymakers and governance	European public institutions (European Commission and associated services, Mission secretariat and European soil observatory, European public officers)	Support policy work with recommendations and knowledge for implementing the Mission and defining the European Commission (EC) agenda regarding soil health, namely on topics related to soil monitoring, LLs and LHs development and priority actions to be implemented. Improve their capacity building regarding data management (under a hypothetically harmonised reporting mechanism across the EU) and their decision-making dependent on soil health indicators values.
	Local (municipalities), regional and National policymakers and their administrations, public institutions	Raise awareness and empower them regarding science-policy and constructive interaction between stakeholders and public governance on Soil Health. Improve capacity building on soil health monitoring to those decision-makers whose actions can affect soil health indicators. Inspire new policy initiatives that support the implementation of sustainable soil management practices.
Public research Funders	Research services of European and national public agencies and institutions	Provide guidance for the definition of the research and innovation agenda regarding soil health (management, monitoring), ecosystem services, land planning and living labs development.
Research community	Mission Soil projects, National research organisations, universities, private organisations with public research projects	Co-develop recommendations and analyse opportunities on soil monitoring framework. Co-create a shared understanding of potential scientific challenges to address for the integration of citizen science (CS) or EO techniques in soil monitoring. Foster information sharing and inter-projects collaboration, including through the involvement in the Mission Soil Clusters.
Education system	Primary, secondary and high school teachers	Help capacity-building of teachers by: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Gathering and disseminating good examples of educational concepts for young people from 6 to 20 years old. · Showcasing soil health science to primary and secondary teachers.

	Vocational Institutes	<p>Help capacity building regarding training on soil health and sustainable management for different land uses in vocational institutes by:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Gathering and sharing examples of educational concepts for young people; · Providing a trans-European analysis on exemplary practices for co-learning in soil health between different actors, including vocational institutes, in various land uses.
	Higher education institutes	<p>Not directly engaged, however the knowledge hub is design to facilitate access to best available knowledge on soil science and challenges regarding soil health, including relevant resources to teachers and student in higher education institutes</p>
Land users / managers / owners	Farmers and agricultural cooperatives	<p>Contribute to empowering through awareness raising and capacity building for soil monitoring and sustainable soil management by:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Fostering their involvement in communities of practices (CoPs) and providing support material to these communities. · Providing a trans-European analysis on exemplary practices for co-learning in soil health between different actors, including soil users and landowners, in agriculture, forest, natural and urban land and soil uses. · Facilitating access to soil resources and examples of good practices for sustainable soil management.
	Land planner and urban planners	
	Forest owners, users and forest cooperatives	
Soil Advisors	Advisors and consultants within agriculture, forestry and land planning (public & private)	<p>Help capacity building by facilitating access to best available science and providing an analysis on soil health awareness, as well as co-learning strategies among agriculture/forestry/urban soil managers, officials, and advisors.</p>
Civil society and citizens	Engaged or aware citizen regarding soil health issues	<p>Foster interaction between citizens and public governance on topics related to sustainable soil management.</p> <p>Provide new opportunities for actions by:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Involving citizen in case studies on CS (questionnaire surveys and workshops conducted in five European Living Labs) · Providing access to best-of online material to inspire and connect citizens.

	Non engaged/non aware citizen regarding soil health issues	Raise awareness and foster citizen engagement regarding soil-related challenges, as well as the dissemination of “best-of” online material to inspire and connect citizens.
Private research funders and investors	Foundations, Private companies, and other investors	Raise awareness and help them to identify priority actions to finance regarding soil health management, monitoring, ecosystem services, land planning and living labs development (e.g. research and R&D actions, service providers for sustainable soil management).
Awareness-raising actors	Science popularisers, artists, journalists, and medias	Facilitate access to soil resources, best available knowledge on soil and examples of educational concepts on soil health, that could be adapted for their audience, to awareness-raising actors addressing topics related to soil health and sustainable soil management. Inform and raise awareness on soil health challenges of other awareness-raising actors that could be interested in addressing topics related to soil health or sustainable soil management (biodiversity, environmental preservation, agriculture).
Industries, supply- and retail actors	Industries, supply and retails companies whose actions can affect soil management (e.g. agri-food processing industry, road and highway construction industry, mining, food suppliers and fast-food organisations)	Raise awareness on their role in soil health improvement. Provide inspiration for taking effective action on soil health across sectors and land uses by: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fostering their involvement in regional and national multi-stakeholder networks (e.g. Soil health national hubs, LLS) • Facilitating access to soil resources and knowledge.
Service providers	Including laboratories, testing centres, certification entities, data centres	Foster involvement of service providers in regional & national multi-actor networks, provide best available knowledge on soil health management, monitoring and land planning.
NGOs and thematic associations	NGOS and association related to preservation of ecosystem services and sustainable soil management	Provide best available knowledge on soil health management, monitoring, ecosystem services and land planning to non- government organisations (NGOs) and associations that could guide their actions on related topics.

Table 1: Targeted stakeholders and objectives for engaging them. The term “The Mission” refers here to the European Mission “A soil deal for Europe”.

Specific roles and multi-stakeholder interfaces	Stakeholders involved that can be reached out	Purpose for engagement
Communities of Practice	Group of stakeholders that gathered to either address an identified threat to soils in their territories by implementing a set of identified actions (e.g. local and regional environmental groups), or to promote the adoption of alternative models to ensure sustainable soil management (e.g. permaculture, community gardening, urban farming)	Foster common understandings, acknowledge differences and discuss ways to support the Mission goals, namely possibilities for engagement in PREPSOIL activities related to CS, NGOs and LLs & LHs as well as feedback on the regional soil needs assessment. Co-create and disseminate best of practice communication and training material for soil-related communities of practices.
(Potential) Living labs and Lighthouses	All stakeholders targeted in PREPSOIL, as they could all be involved in living labs	Provide support material for LLs & LHs development and sustainability including examples of possible business plans, as well as a “toolbox” to accelerate the adoption, maturity and optimise the running of the Mission LLs & LHs under different land use contexts.
National Contact Points	National Contact Points and associated networks, represented by national authorities or stakeholders from the scientific community	To inform National Contact Points on PREPSOIL’s outputs related to living labs that could help them provide guidance to their national community.
Soil advocates	Individuals or organisations with technical expertise related to soil management, seeking to advance sustainable soil management (e.g. land managers and soil users, advisors, national park officers, scientists, agricultural journalists, civil servants with relevant experience, ...).	Collaborate on raising awareness on the challenges that European soils are experiencing and promote sustainable soil management.

Table 2: Specific roles and multi-stakeholder interfaces targeted in PREPSOIL

2.3 Stakeholder Engagement: Overview

WP	Task	Main Responsible	Contributing partners
WP1	T1.2	ACTA	

Stakeholder engagement during the project was realised through different approaches, mainly by building on partners' own networks, producing open calls, reaching out to former projects or building on existing networks, and relying on motivated stakeholders primarily engaged, ready to mobilize their own network to support PREPSOIL engagement efforts. This last approach was especially helpful for actions at the local level such as the workshop in WP2 or surveys dissemination in WP6.

2.3.1 Main engagement activities implemented between M1 and M18

Main engagement activities in PREPSOIL between M1 and M18 are described in the previous Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication plan (D1.2). They mainly targeted local and national stakeholders with:

- More than 500 regional and local stakeholders directly engaged as part of the WP2 soil needs assessments (interview or participation to a workshop);
- Communities of Practice, focusing on agricultural, natural and urban land uses, with the registration of six communities of practice on PREPSOIL website, from UK, Spain, Slovakia, France and Belgium (WP6);
- Education stakeholders, mainly primary, secondary teachers through WP6 call for best teaching practices (WP6);
- Existing LLs, to gather inputs from mature living labs (workshops) and support the establish of a map of existing LLs (open online survey) (WP4);
- Soil advocates across Europe. A call was open since the beginning of PREPSOIL projects to allow voluntary stakeholders to apply to become a PREPSOIL Soil Advocate (WP3&6).

While the initial plan in D1.1 expected to facilitate engagement of national and regional stakeholders by engaging first with trans-European associations (beyond PREPSOIL partners), it was eventually not followed through, partners rather building on their networks and on motivated local contacts, able to share and foster local stakeholder engagement through their own network.

2.3.2 Main engagement activities implemented between M19 and M36

Main engagement activities in PREPSOIL between M19 and M36 targeted stakeholders from the European level to the local level with:

- Engagement of municipalities, private and public landowners and users, advisory services, vocational schools, and scientists in seven different countries, through online surveys and focus group interviews with farmers and advisors to gather inputs to support improvement of co-learning systems (WP6);

- Engagement of stakeholders from the education system through a second call for examples of best teaching practices (WP6);
- Interactions with stakeholders involved in LLs as part of WP4 with the development of a toolbox for living labs in WP4 and a participatory process to co-design a business model canvas for living labs and lighthouses;
- More engagement of stakeholders involved in Communities of Practices, with now 20 Communities of Practice registered on the PREPSOIL website and 80+ videos with engaged groups of farmers, gardeners, forest workers, advisors, researchers and teachers (WP6);
- Dialogue and a co-creation process with over 20 Mission Soil projects, multiple European institutions and stakeholders responsible for soil health monitoring at the Member States level as part of WP5, to identify priority training needs and develop a comprehensive and modular training curriculum on soil health, designed to prepare public authorities, technicians, and policymakers for the challenges posed by the forthcoming Soil Monitoring Law (SML);
- Interactions with the Mission Board, the Mission secretariat, country representatives and existing national hubs to foster the development of Soil Mirror Groups (WP1), as explained in sub-section 2.3.3 Focus on National Hubs Expansion.

The main resulting outputs of these engagement activities and the associated communication, dissemination and exploitation actions are detailed in the next two main sections of the document.

2.3.3 Focus on National Hubs Expansion

2.3.3.1 Description of the work and adaptations

In the previous plan presented in D1.2, it was expected that PREPSOIL would support the Mirror Group dynamic, with strengthened starting at M20 (Feb. 2024), as the publication of the Mission Board's set of recommendations for Mirror Group establishment was planned early 2024.

While the final Mission Board's set of recommendations were released at M21 (available here: <https://mission-soil-platform.ec.europa.eu/index.php/resource-library/mission-soil-boards-set-recommendations-establishment-national-mirror-groups>), PREPSOIL started this effort as planned especially through interaction with EJP SOIL, to support their mapping of existing National Soil Health hubs, ensure knowledge sharing about the progress regarding the Mirror Group dynamic with EJP SOIL partners and their National Soil Hub, and even co-organise an event with the French National Hub in March 2024 to foster the development of this hub into a Mirror Group, with a presentation of the guidelines and discussions focusing on the national specificities.

The mid-term review (covering M1 to M18) highlighted expectations and needs from the Mission Secretariat to know more about the existing Mirror Groups, as a prerequisite to the effort of Mirror Group establishment and development. Therefore, in collaboration with PREPSOIL and the Mission Board, the Mission Secretariat sent an EU survey through the Strategic Programme Committee (SPC) of the Mission in July 2024, open until September 2024. The Mission Secretariat then shared the results with PREPSOIL, that started analysing the survey responses.

PREPSOIL work to build an overview of existing Mirror Group, or groups carrying out similar activities, was then organised in four main steps:

1: Sharing the analysis and recommendations with the Mission Board and Mission Secretariat.

Preliminary findings from the initial survey (22 countries responded) were shared with the Mission Secretariat and SPC members during a meeting in November 2024, and with Mission Board members during a meeting in February 2025.

Continuous interaction with the Mission Secretariat allowed PREPSOIL to ensure alignment and knowledge sharing throughout the process.

2: Organising bilateral meetings with voluntary country representatives involved in the SPC, suggesting them to invite any relevant participant including, for country represented in EJP SOIL, the National Soil Health hub coordinator of their country.

These meetings were organised during February 2025 and allowed PREPSOIL to gather more input from 16 countries about their situation regarding Mirror Group establishment.

3. Disseminating the results of this work into the production of a short report and the organisation of a webinar.

This work was carried out until the end of the project and is concluded with the production of the report and the organisation of the webinar in June 2025. Both the report and the webinar material (recording, communication support) are available on PREPSOIL website: <https://prepsoil.eu/events/soil-mission-mirror-groups-where-do-we-stand>.

This work, identified as one of the KERs highlighted in section 4, was also presented during the PREPSOIL final event in May 2025.

4. In parallel, and based on the needs and opportunities identified in the interviews with the SPC members, PREPSOIL was expected to work to organise interactions with the Mirror Group (if any) or the National Soil Health hub of the country represented in PREPSOIL consortium to foster establishment of a Mirror Group or the development of existing Mirror Groups (getting closer to the Mission board Recommendations, sharing examples and practices used in other groups, ...).

Those specific interactions were mainly ensured for countries involved in both steps of PREPSOIL work, which were not all represented in PREPSOIL. Thus, seven partners (Denmark, France, Germany, Italy, Norway, Sweden and The Netherlands) had direct interactions with national representatives in their country, either by participating in the bilateral meetings, having direct dialogue, or having a meeting with them and their national hub.

However, most countries were in a phase where they needed to discuss and align at the ministerial level before moving forward, which hampered the capability of PREPSOIL partners to organise more and broader national events, as initially anticipated.

2.3.3.2 Perspectives

PREPSOIL worked to align and adapt its initial plans related to National Hub expansion to the new dynamic of Mirror Group and the current needs of the Mission Secretariat. The material will remain easily available to all interested parties, and a key stakeholder, the Mission Secretariat, has expressed during the PREPSOIL webinar organised in June 2025 its ambition to continue to encourage and support the development of these groups, building on this overview and examples of existing Mirror Groups as a way to inspire and help other groups. This should be helped by the current European context that could bring an important incentive, as establishing or developing Mirror Groups or similar organisations are a good exercise to be more prepared for the future soil monitoring law that could be adopted by the end of the year.

2.4 Ethical aspects, lessons learned and perspectives

WP	Task	Main Responsible	Contributing partners
WP1	T1.2	ACTA	AU

2.4.1 Ethical aspects

Stakeholder mapping and engagement included a template for a consent form to help partners with engaging stakeholders in respect of GDPR principles.

Data on stakeholders were stored on the PREPSOIL SharePoint, as described in the data management plan of the project (last version being D7.3).

The work done in the Soil Mission Support project (SMS) was also highlighted for example and inspiration when approaching engagement activities, as the project provided a guide for engaging actors in land and soil management with key steps to follow and engagement principles, example of tools that can be used to engage stakeholders, as well as examples of stakeholder engagement in previous European projects.

Partners also took into consideration the feedback from the Ethical Advisor, whose work and observations are available in its reports (D8.2, D8.3), regarding ethical aspects of their work and their engagement activities, especially when dealing with personal information. In this regard, anonymisation or pseudonymisation were encouraged whenever possible.

While inclusivity was not clearly discussed at the early stage of the project, feedback from our Ethic Advisor supported partners in considering more clearly these selection criteria.

Overall, efforts were made for transparency regarding our work and selection criteria for stakeholders, although more emphasis could have been made from the beginning to reflect on whether individual criteria such as gender, age, professional background, cultural background, etc. were relevant for the different activities.

2.4.2 Lessons learned and perspectives

As a CSA addressing the overall Mission Soil, PREPSOIL activities targeted a wide range of different stakeholders, from the European to the local level, to address a diversity of topics and thematics, making it difficult to adopt a completely unified and fixed approach regarding stakeholder engagement. However, the choice to adopt a flexible approach, with key guiding principles, while keeping on monitoring the different engagement actions, seems to be appropriate. It allowed project partners to adapt and adjust engagement methods to the needs and challenges specific to the stakeholders targeted and the associated actions.

While building on personal contacts is usually a very efficient method to engage relevant stakeholders, it can restrain the overall representativity of stakeholders engaged, with a stronger involvement of stakeholders already aware or engaged in various projects.

Open calls and digital communication (social networks, newsletter) can be interesting to engage stakeholders, especially at the European or national level, if a specific and homogeneous geographic coverage is not necessarily expected.

Engaging stakeholders, possibly from our personal contacts, to ask them to support the identification and engagement of other stakeholders, similarly to the snowball method, can be a good way to engage relevant stakeholders while still building on an existing trust. At the local level, when working in a specific territory for instance, it seems to be one of the most efficient ways to gain trust and engagement. However, this is also the most time-consuming approach, as it implies to find motivated and committed stakeholders (or to motivate them), ready to support the project actions with their own network.

In the end, diversifying the engagement approaches to reach out to stakeholders seems best to ensure results. Having the opportunity to engage stakeholders with a clear example of what would be the results of their efforts, highlighting the benefits for them but also how these efforts matter is key to gaining engagement. In this regard, one of the challenges for European projects is to prepare the post-project period and to enable the stakeholders involved to envision how, even if the project will not be able to support them in the future, they can still build on the activities they get involved in.

3. DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION

WP	Task	Main Responsible	Contributing partners
WP1	T1.1	AU	TrustIT

3.1 Introduction

WP	Task	Main Responsible	Contributing partners
WP1	T1.1	AU	TrustIT

A dynamic strategy and plan for the CDE of PREPSOIL output was designed, implemented and adjusted throughout the duration of the project period. The strategy identified a list of KPIs relevant to the overall project ambition. Most have been achieved, some surpassed and only few have not been completed. This report will describe our activities from M1 to M36 in detail and along the way ask the important questions: “What was achieved?” and “what are lessons learned?”

Following the Consortium Meeting held in Budapest in October 2024, WP1 once again developed an updated CDE plan leading up to the conclusion of the project by end of June 2025. This updated plan includes a consolidated overview of KPIs, detailed descriptions of collaborative procedures (Appendix 01), and a Weekly Activity Plan (Appendix 02) designed to ensure consistent, timely, and impact-oriented communication and dissemination efforts.

Decentralised dissemination activities and focus on project results

Drawing inspiration from the EJP Soil’s National Communication Representatives (NCRs) and with the aim of maximising impact, all project partners were encouraged to appoint a dedicated Communication Representative. This structure facilitated broad-based communication, leveraging each partner’s network to reach a diverse, multilingual target audience.

The updated CDE plan also signified a strategic shift towards stronger emphasis on project results across news articles, newsletters, and social media platforms.

Data and statistics

Availability and discoverability of PREPSOIL outputs and relevant information was ensured through a SEO-optimised [website](#) and a central [Knowledge Hub](#), supporting long-term access via [Zenodo integration](#). The inclusion of [PREPSOIL TV](#), with engaging video content directly embedded on the website, successfully encouraged visitors to remain longer and explore more of the project’s results. These strategic efforts led to the project surpassing all website-related KPIs, maintaining a large and engaged audience for PREPSOIL content. To further maximise reach, especially in the final phase of the project, a targeted Google Ads campaign was deployed to drive additional traffic to the Knowledge Hub.

Complementing the website, the PREPSOIL newsletter achieved a high open rate of 34.5%—well above the industry benchmark of 20–25%. This reflects a consistently high-value and relevant

content offering that kept subscribers engaged and ensured ongoing discoverability of project updates and results.

The dissemination value of engagement events

While a few KPIs proved challenging to achieve, the overall outcome has been a success in establishing a workflow, a solid structure, and commitment that has ensured the fulfilment of the WP1 objectives. An example of this engagement is the project's presence at third-party events as described in section 3.8 of this deliverable. These events have provided opportunities to reach audiences beyond the existing PREPSOIL newsletter and social media followers, while also creating a more lasting impact than the typically brief interactions on social media.

3.2 Check List of the goals and KPI's of T1.1

WP	Task	Main Responsible	Contributing partners
WP1	T1.1	AU	TrustIT

The check list below contains a full overview of the goals, objectives and KPI's related to T1.1. Each KPI is thoroughly discussed in the chapters below.

ORIGIN/SOURCE	GOAL / KPI	DEADLINE	STATUS
GA Part A, T1.1	“produce a coherent plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication”	M7	Done
GA Part A, T1.1	“coordinate the execution of CDE-activities in the project in a timely manner with an impact-oriented approach”	Continuously	Done
GA Part B, 2.2.1	“enable the means for interaction, knowledge sharing, and peer-learning needed to execute the work plan”	Continuously	Done
GA Part B, 2.2.1	“provide the means for partners to interact with stakeholders via workshops, webinars, interviews and other offline and online channels”	Continuously	Done
GA Part B, 2.2.1	“disseminate project results to target audiences”	Continuously	Done
GA Part B, 2.2.1	“maximize the visibility of the Mission among society at large (citizens, policymakers, businesses)”	Continuously	Done
DCE plan, Nov. 2024, KPI	12 newsletters	M36	Done
DCE plan, Nov. 2024, KPI	Total community database: 2,000 D1.1: 500 by M12, 1200 by M24, 2000 by M36	M36	Done
DCE plan, Nov. 2024, KPI	6 press releases	M36	Done
DCE plan, Nov. 2024, KPI	Total of 2,200 social media members	M36	Done
DCE plan, Nov. 2024, KPI	Twitter: 1,000 followers, 300,000 impressions, 500 tweets	M36	Missed
DCE plan, Nov. 2024, KPI	LinkedIn: 1,200 followers, 50,000 impressions	M36	Done
DCE plan, Nov. 2024, KPI	Youtube: 80 videos, 100 views per video	M36	Done
DCE plan, Nov. 2024, KPI	80 videos	M36	Done
DCE plan, Nov. 2024, KPI	1 project branding package with logos, templates, and collaterals available.	M1	Done
DCE plan, Nov. 2024, KPI	3 fliers	M36	Done
DCE plan, Nov. 2024, KPI	3 posters	M36	Done
DCE plan, Nov. 2024, KPI	2 roll up banners	M36	Done
DCE plan, Nov. 2024, KPI	30 presentations	M36	Done
DCE plan, Nov. 2024, KPI	30 presences at third party physical and virtual events	M36	Done
DCE plan, Nov. 2024, KPI	500 avg. downloads per individual resource in Zenodo	M36	In progress
DCE plan, Nov. 2024, KPI	Total visitors 15,000 on website	M36	Done
DCE plan, Nov. 2024, KPI	Sessions per month 3,000 on website	M36	Done
DCE plan, Nov. 2024, KPI	5 peer-reviewed articles	M36	In progress

Table 3: Goals, objectives and KPI's related to T1.1

3.3 News pieces and press releases

WP	Task	Main Responsible	Contributing partners
WP1	T1.1	AU	

KPI	Deadline	Status
6 press releases	M36	Done

Work and achievements

Throughout the project there has been a natural development towards a stronger communication and dissemination focus on project results. With strong support from the project coordinators and in cooperation with WP-leaders and Task-leaders, relevant topics have been selected for dissemination. Primarily topics related to events, relevant informative or exploitable outputs and deliverables, but in praxis anything deemed relevant to the target audience. Recurring meetings with WP1 and WP3 have coordinated the production of news pieces and the plan for dissemination in more detail.

6 press releases have been sent out via the nonprofit news-release distribution platform EurekAlert! operated by the [American Association for the Advancement of Science](#) (AAAS). Press releases have been used when there was a need to communicate to a broader selection of stakeholders and target audiences on the margins of PREPSOIL’s loyal group of followers of the newsletter and social media accounts.

KPI’s, data and analysis

A total of 42 news pieces (M35) have been written and published during the project period. Dividing these news pieces into two groups focusing on “Calls and activities” and “Results”, shows a natural progression as project results are published.

	M4-6	M7-9	M10-12	M13-15	M16-18	M19-21	M22-24	M25-27	M28-30	M31-33	M34-35
Calls/activities	XXX	XXX	XX		XXXXX	XXXX	X				XXX
Results	X	X	X	X	XXX			XXX	XX	XXXXXXXX	XX

Table 4: Number of news pieces divided according to content

A number of 6 press releases have been sent out from January to June 2025. Following the analysis of news pieces above, the topics in the press releases are dominated by calls and activities - always, however, leading to dissemination and exploitation of project results.

Headline	Date
PREPSOIL and SOILL-Startup Host Online training on Business Model Canvas	Jun 2, 2025
Empowering Soil Innovation: The PREPSOIL Toolbox Helps Living Labs Grow	Jun 2, 2025
PREPSOIL launches assessment tool for soil living lab and lighthouse initiatives	Apr. 22, 2025
PREPSOIL Final Event: Facilitating the deployment of the Mission Soil across European regions	Apr. 22, 2025
PREPSOIL promotes soil literacy through education	Feb. 7, 2025
PREPSOIL webinar explores soil literacy among youth: Why it matters and how educators can foster it	Jan. 8, 2025

Table 5: Press releases send out

Lessons learned and final perspectives

Efforts to produce and communicate strong interest in soil related topics have proven successful, reflecting a clear interest in the PREPSOIL project and results. Looking ahead, it is important to consider how internal and external communication are prioritised throughout the project lifecycle. In the early stages, internal communication tends to be more critical, while in later phases, the focus shifts toward external communication to disseminate project outcomes and deliverables. A dynamic CDE-strategy and plan should be designed to adapt to these evolving communication needs.

Support and understanding from the Consortium partners of CDE-related activities have been essential to the overall progress of WP1, particularly in relation to dissemination efforts. It is advised that communication professionals design and lead CDE related activities, but also that they ensure the basic understanding amongst all consortium partners in the use of relevant communication channels. Especially social media platforms.

3.4 Community database

WP	Task	Main Responsible	Contributing partners
WP1	T1.1	AU and TrustIT	

KPI	Deadline	Status
Total community database: 2000 by M36	M36	Done

To work with stakeholders as a community in a project like PREPSOIL brings several strategic, operational, and social benefits that can greatly enhance the project's impact, sustainability, and relevance. Building a stakeholder community fosters trust, mutual understanding, and open dialogue which leads to wider uptake, greater visibility, and increased policy or societal impact.

The work on both frequency and content of the PREPSOIL newsletter shows dedication and thoroughness, and the opening rate reported below indicates a strong connection and interest from the PREPSOIL community. The same qualities can be said about the PREPSOIL presence on social media, and the gradually intensified work with LinkedIn has helped build the community around PREPSOIL.

KPI's, data and analysis

As stated in the previous CDE-strategies, D1.1 and D1.2, PREPSOIL has from the early stages been able to create a consolidated community of people with interest in the key results and goals.

Type	Results by M36
Community on Social Media	2320
Community in Newsletter	1684
No. of stakeholders in the PREPSOIL database	800+
Community database in total	4804+

Table 6: Members of the community database

Lessons learned and final perspectives

It is important to use the most relevant platforms and interact with the community members where they are. During the three-year project period of PREPSOIL, we have seen how electronics, politics and the media landscape evolves in sometimes unforeseen ways. This requires an adaptive and agile approach - and this is the approach taken in WP1.

3.5 Newsletters

WP	Task	Main Responsible	Contributing partners
WP1	T1.1	TrustIT	AU

KPI	Deadline	Status
12 newsletters	M36	Done

Work and achievements

The newsletter plays a key role in PREPSOIL’s communication and dissemination strategy. It serves as an effective tool to reach a diverse target audience, including stakeholders, partners, and the public. By regularly sharing updates, achievements, and upcoming activities, the newsletter helps to raise awareness, promote engagement, and ensure transparency. It also supports the wider dissemination of project outcomes, contributing to the overall visibility and impact of the initiative.

Since the beginning of the project, a total of 12 newsletters (as of M36) have been produced. Table 6 below summarises the newsletters.

Issue	Date of Publication	Link
1	6 June 2023	Welcome to the first PREPSOIL Newsletter!
2	15 November 2025	Welcome to the PREPSOIL Newsletter N°2
3	15 January 2024	Welcome to the PREPSOIL Newsletter N°3
4	22 February 2024	Welcome to the PREPSOIL Newsletter N°4
5	13 May 2024	Latest news on the PREPSOIL mobile app, workshop in Brussels on LL Business Models, PREPSOIL summer events and more
6	1 August 2024	Launch of the PREPSOIL app, New Report on Soil Monitoring the PREPSOIL Knowledge Hub and future events
7	16 January 2025	New Webinar on Soil Literacy Among Youth, news on Europe’s Living Labs & Lighthouses and YouTube videos on Advancing Soil Sustainability
8	17 March 2025	News on Soil Literacy Through Education and Harmonised Soil Monitoring Framework Across Europe, & new YouTube videos on Advancing Soil Sustainability
9	27 March 2025	News on PREPSOIL Knowledge Hub: Now Also Available in Your Pocket & Feasibility of Satellite Technology for Soil Health Monitoring in Europe
10	29 April 2025	PREPSOIL Final Event in Brussels & new Assessment Tool for Soil Living Lab and Lighthouse Initiatives!

11	29 May 2025	PREPSOIL Final Event in Brussels, Soil Network Europe continues the exploitation of PREPSOIL results, Online Training on Business Model Canvas & PREPSOIL Toolbox
12	6 June 2025	Explore how PREPSOIL is advancing soil health through three upcoming events, featuring new digital tools, capacity-building sessions, and insights into national Mirror Groups driving the EU Soil Mission forward.

Table 7: List of PREPSOIL Newsletters

In addition, the newsletters have been produced in line with the project’s branding guidelines. This ensures a consistent visual identity and tone across all communications, reinforcing the project’s image and making it easily recognisable to the target audience. The platform chosen is Mailchimp.

KPI’s, data and analysis

The total number of current subscribers is 1684. The number of subscribers has positively evolved over time with picks during events such as webinars, workshops and in person-events. Figure 3 and Figure 4 below show the audience performance and the tot subscriptions growth in the past month. It is possible to see an increment in the month of May with a positive increment of 88.4%.

Contacts breakdown

May 18, 2025 - June 16, 2025

Channel summary Email

Total subscribers

1,684 ↑ 88.4% compared to last year

Day Week Month

Total subscribers by channel

Email only 100% 1,684

Figure 3 Contact breakdown of PREPSOIL Newsletter audience

Figure 4: Total net subscriptions growth

Figure 5: Monitor Performance of PREPSOIL Newsletters

As can be seen from the Figure 5 above, in the last year (June 2024-June 2025), the total number of emails sent is 6,807, with an open-rate of 34.5% whereas the number of unsubscribe rates is low, around 0.82%. An open rate of 34.5% for newsletters is a strong result, well above the average benchmark of 20-22%¹. This indicates that the audience of the newsletters finds the content relevant and interesting. In addition, the unsubscription rate remains low at around 0.82%, reinforcing the idea that the content is in line with readers' expectations and interests.

A click- rate of 7% for newsletters is a positive indicator of engagement. This means that subscribers not only open the emails but also take action and interact with the content (such as reading an article, registering for an event or visiting a page on the website), thus they seem to be interested and enticed to find out more about the topics covered. This result, together with an open rate of 34.5% and a low unsubscription rate of 0.82%, reflects a valuable and well-functioning communication channel.

Lessons learned and final perspectives

The newsletter is an important tool for enhancing the visibility of the project and disseminating its results. By providing regular updates in a clear and accessible format, it ensures that key findings, progress, and outcomes are effectively communicated to a broad audience. This helps to maximise the reach and impact of the project, fostering greater awareness, encouraging stakeholder engagement, and supporting the uptake of results beyond the project's regular network.

¹ <https://www.campaignmonitor.com/resources/knowledge-base/what-are-good-email-metrics/>

3.6 Social media

WP	Task	Main Responsible	Contributing partners
WP1	T1.1	TrustIT	AU

KPI	Deadline	Status
Total of 2,200 social media members	M36	Done
Twitter: 1,000 followers, 300,000 impressions, 500 tweets	M36	Missed
LinkedIn: 1,200 followers, 50,000 impressions	M36	Done

Work and achievements

Social media	Link
X	@prepsoil
LinkedIn	PREPSOIL - Preparing for the "Soil Deal for Europe" Mission
YouTube	PREPSOIL YouTube channel

Table 8: PREPSOIL Social Media Channels

LinkedIn

LinkedIn is a valuable channel to share PREPSOIL's journey in a more dynamic and engaging way. LinkedIn has been an essential platform for PREPSOIL to connect with a wide professional audience and share the project's efforts to promote soil health in Europe. LinkedIn allowed us to reach key stakeholders who are of primary importance to the project, such as land managers, researchers and practitioners, with targeted and relevant content.

We maintained a constant posting frequency of about once a week, with increased activity during major events, workshops and webinars.

Below is an example of one of the LinkedIn posts that best performed in the past year (June 2024-June 2025) with over 44.400 impressions.

Image 1: Examples of LinkedIn Posts

X (formerly Twitter)

From the beginning of the project Twitter was expected to play a key role in the communication strategy, providing a fast and widely used platform to share updates, connect with interested communities and participate in ongoing conversations. We maintained a regular publication schedule of about one post per week, with increased activity at events, conferences and webinars. This has helped us increase visibility at strategic moments and engage both followers and a wider audience interested in the project topics. Due to the real-time nature of X (formerly Twitter) and its wide reach, we were able to quickly share news and highlights and publish live posts during ongoing events.

After the change in name, ownership and algorithm, X has played a decreasing role. Focus from WP1 has increasingly shifted towards LinkedIn instead.

Image 2: Examples of X posts

YouTube

YouTube proved to be an effective platform to share the project work in a more visual and accessible format, especially regarding soil and soil health awareness. The opportunity to have videos and interviews allowed us to concretely show initiatives, opportunities on soil and to be able to expand the message. Content was published periodically. This allowed us to show project activities on the ground, bring the voices of experts to the fore and share real life stories about soil projects across Europe and beyond.

PREPSOIL YouTube channel counts 4 playlists, each focusing on a specific topic. They are:

1. Advancing Soil Sustainability Video Series (68 videos)
2. Interviews (5 videos)
3. Best Teaching Practices (7 videos)
4. Regional soil needs workshops (8 videos)

KPI's, data and analysis

	KPI to monitor	M36	Achieved?	Numbers
X	Followers	1.000	NO	700
LinkedIn	Followers	1.200	YES	1620
	Impressions	50.000	YES	62,136
Youtube	Videos	>80	NO	88
	Views	100 views/video across channels	YES	137,5

Table 9: PREPSOIL Social Media KPIs

LinkedIn counts 1,620 followers, whereas X counts 700 followers (as of M36). Figure 6 below shows the Impressions trend on LinkedIn in the last year (June 2024-June 2025), while Table 9 below shows the most relevant factors for the complete analysis of LinkedIn's performance in the last year (June 2024-June 2025), those are: Impressions, reactions, Comments and reposts.

Highlights

Data for 6/2/2024 - 6/1/2025

62,136

Impressions

1,387

Reactions

49

Comments

43

Reposts

Metrics

Impressions ▾

Figure 6: Engagement rate of PREPSOIL LinkedIn channel in the last year (June 2024-June 2024)

Impressions	Reactions	Comments	Reposts
62,136	1387	49	43

Table 10: The most relevant factors for the LinkedIn performance in the last year (June 2024-June 2025)

From the data shown above, it is possible to state that in the last year (June 2024-June 2025), the LinkedIn page recorded 62.136 impressions in total: 38.214 organic and 23.922 sponsored. The high share of organic impressions highlights the strong quality of the content and audience engagement on LinkedIn without paid support. Sponsored impressions, on the other hand, reflect a targeted effort to extend visibility in a strategic manner. This balanced mix suggests a healthy approach, combining consistent engagement with selective investment in promotion.

At M36, the PREPSOIL YouTube Channel counts 76 videos published. In the last year (June 2024-June 2025), the channel got a total of 7.373 views. The image below summaries the analytics:

Figure 7: Analytics of PREPSOIL YouTube Channel in the last year (June 2024-June 2025)

Lessons learned and final perspectives

In general, the LinkedIn, X and YouTube campaigns had a positive response. On LinkedIn, the most successful posts were those related to events, such as organised webinars and the final project event. Re-posts were also more frequent for posts with topics involving different partners and stakeholders. These posts helped us highlight project updates, present partner activities and stimulate conversations about the importance of healthy soils and sustainable land use. By sharing insights, tools and results in an accessible and engaging way, we fostered greater recognition of the need for responsible soil management and the actions needed to protect this essential resource. The most frequently used types of content were articles, promotion of events, multimedia and publications.

3.7 Video

WP	Task	Main Responsible	Contributing partners
WP1	T1.1	TrustIT	NIBIO

KPI	Deadline	Status
YouTube: 80 videos, 100 views per video	M36	Done
80 videos	M36	Done

Work and achievements

Videos are more engaging than static text. The combination of motion, sound, and visuals can capture attention more easily and keep viewers interested. This is especially important when trying to explain concepts that might otherwise be dry or difficult to grasp. Videos can show "how-to" instructions or demonstrations in real time, along with multilanguage subtitles to make them accessible to a wider audience.

During its lifetime, PREPSOIL released several videos through its YouTube Channel and the PREPSOIL TV, organised in specific playlists (see Table 10) to facilitate the overall experience and research. They represented an important way to provide to the user more detailed information about several activities from the PREPSOIL project. A full list of the Task 6.1 videos can be found in Appendix 03.

Category	Description	N° Videos
Best Teaching Practices (T6.2)	Interviews made to the winners where they provided more details on the pedagogic practices, they organised in the classrooms	7
Communities of Practices (T6.1)	Interviews made to the people behind CoPs implemented across several European countries, to inspire others to promote similar activities in their locations.	47
Living Labs & Lighthouses	Overview of main activities performed in different LLs and LHs in Europe and how they have been helping to improve soil sustainability	8
Soil Advocates (T6.1)	Testimonials of soil sustainability experts who share their knowledge and experience regarding soil management and increasing soil literacy in Europe	7
Regional Soil Needs Workshops (WP2)	Provide a short glimpse of the moments in specific workshops, as well as interviews providing a generic overview of the conclusions achieved in certain workshops	7
Interviews (WP1)	Interviews made to each PREPSOIL WP leaders	5
TOTAL		81

Table 11: Overview of PREPSOIL Videos. The number of videos is counted by mid-June. Some videos awaiting revision uploaded on the YouTube channel before 30 June, meeting the objective of WP6.

Videos were embedded in specific sections of PREPSOIL website (e.g. [CoPs](#), [Winner of Teaching Practices](#), amongst others), to enhance user experience, improve engagement, and boost the effectiveness of the content (see Image 3). Important to mention that each video, before publication, were approved by the PREPSOIL editorial board, which checked the quality of each video as well as the accuracy of the subtitles made for each one.

Image 3: PREPSOIL videos embed in specific pages (CoP page left, Winner of Teaching Practices page centre, Soil Needs Assessment Workshop page right)

PREPSOIL videos were promoted on project official social media channels, as well as through the newsletters, to maximise even further their outreach.

Image 4: PREPSOIL Videos being promoted on X (left), LinkedIn (centre) and newsletter (right)

KPI's, data and analysis

With a total of 80 number of videos made available, by the time of writing this report, each one reached an average of 137,5 views, surpassing the KPI of 100 views per video in average. Considering the videos will keep being available after PREPSOIL conclusion, the number of views for each view will keep increasing.

Description	KPI by M36	Result
N° Videos on YouTube	80	88
N° Views on YouTube per video	100	137,5

Table 12: PREPSOIL Videos KPIs vs achieved results

Lessons learned and final perspectives

Videos represent an excellent way to get viewers' attention and disseminate project output in an engaging and effective manner.

3.8 Printed materials and events

WP	Task	Main Responsible	Contributing partners
WP1	T1.1	TrustIT	AU

KPI	Deadline	Status
1 project branding package with logos, templates, and collaterals available.	M36	Done
3 fliers	M36	Done
3 posters	M36	Done
2 roll up banners	M36	Done
30 presentations	M36	Done
30 presences at third party physical and virtual events	M36	Done

Work and achievements

Concerning communication materials, besides the logo, a complete communication toolkit was made available to the consortium and the overall PREPSOIL community. Over the months, a series of materials for digital use and for printing were to promote PREPSOIL at physical and online events. Examples are described in Table 12 below.

Type of Material	Name and link	KPI	Qt.
Project branding package		1	1
Flyers	Generic Flyer Communities of Practice and Multilingual Soil Knowledge Hub PREPSOIL Final Results Foldable Flyer	3	4
Posters / PREPSOIL Generic	Poster 1 - Generic Poster 2 – Living Labs and Lighthouses Poster 3 – Living Labs and Lighthouses (French) Poster 4 – Communities of Practice		
Posters / Soil Needs Assessment	Post-Mining - Vzhodna Zasavje (Slovenia) Dense Urbanism – Noord Amsterdam (The Netherlands) Post-Mining - Upper Silesia (Poland) Reforestation - Vysocina (Czech Republic) Peatlands - Eastern and Midland (Ireland) Alpine Tourism - Lautaret-Oisans Alpine region (France) Agro-Forestry in DEHESA - Extremadura (Spain) Forest Tourism South East - Antalya (Turkey) Forest Peatland Northeast - Soomaa (Estonia) Kryckland - Upper Norrland (Sweden) Mixed Farming North - Trondelag (Norway) Organic Mixed Farming East - Del-Alföld (Hungary) Large Scale Annual Cropping - Emilia-Romagna (Italy) Annual Cropping North, East Denmark (Denmark) Wine farming - Aquitaine (France) Annual Cropping Central Europe - Brandenburg (Germany)	3	24

	Olive Tree Cultivation - Andalusia (Spain) Irrigated Arable Farming - Valencia (Spain) Sheep Agrosilvopastoral Farming - Tirso Valley (Sardegna, Italy) Cow Dairy Farming - Gelderland (The Netherlands)		
Roll up banners	PREPSOIL Roll-up Aug2022-1 0.pdf PREPSOIL Roll-up Final Event	2	2
Presentations at third party physical/virtual events	See table 13	30	76
Give Aways	Branded Notebooks Pencils Cotton bag	3	3
Others	Soil Needs and Drivers of Change Across Europe and Land Use Types PREPSOIL Mobile App Booklet PREPSOIL Final Results Booklet	N/A	3

Table 13: PREPSOIL Communication Materials produced

During the project lifetime, PREPSOIL had an active role in over 70 events, surpassing the initial plan to be involved in 30 events across Europe. Table 13 provides an overview of all events where PREPSOIL was involved.

As said in previous iterations of PREPSOIL communication and dissemination deliverable, presence at events was achieved through presentations, as well as participation in panel sessions, exhibition stands and posters. Thanks to the consistent presence at events, PREPSOIL was able to widen European audiences.

N	Date	Event title	Location	Audience	Activity
1	Jun. 2022	ERIAFF Annual Conference	Greece	Regional Authorities	Presentation
2	Aug. 2022	ECOMONDO	Italy	Circular Economy Industry	Presentation
3	Sep. 2022	Open Living Lab Days 2022	Italy	Policy makers, companies, entrepreneurs, academics, Living Lab representatives and innovators	Panel participation, Poster exhibition
4	Sep. 2022	Terra Madre Salone del Gusto	Italy	Students, citizens, farmers, policy makers	Communication Materials at partner's exhibition stand
5	Sep. 2022	National Soil Hub Meeting	Online	Researchers in Hungary	Presentation
6	Sep. 2022	SMS final event	Belgium	Policy makers, practitioners, scientists,	Presentation
7	Oct. 2022	Course for Journalists about soil	Italy	Journalists and Policy Makers	Presentation
8	Oct. 2022	2nd EUSO Stakeholders Forum	Online	Policy makers, soil and soil-related scientists, local actors, civil society representatives and citizens.	Presentation
9	Nov. 2022	Spanish Soil Network Event	Spain	Soil Scientists	Presentation

10	Dec. 2022	Soil for secondary school science teachers Workshop	Italy	Science Teachers	Presentation
11	Dec. 2022	Dalla Terra alla terra	Italy	Policy makers, companies, academia, media	Presentation
12	Jan. 2023	Soilidarity Workshop: EU Soil Health Living Labs	Online	Living Labs	Presentation
13	Jan. 2023	1st European Mission Forum EMiF: "Making Missions Work"	Online	Policy Makers	Presentation
14	Jan. 2023	Horizon Europe 2023 National Info Day	Online	Researchers	Presentation
15	Jan. 2023	SOIL O-LIVE project KoM	Spain	Practitioners, scientists, SOIOLIVE project partners	Presentation
16	Feb. 2023	Dutch Union for Soil Science webinar: Soil Health in (policy) perspective	Online	Scientists, policymakers, students, advisors	Presentation
17	Feb. 2023	GenB Common Ground Camp on Bioeconomy education	Greece	Teaching Community	Presentation
18	Mar. 2023	International Congress S4agro 2023	Portugal	Researchers, scientists, policy makers, agro-industrial SMEs, professionals and students	Presentation
19	Mar. 2023	Nati00ns Italy event	Italy	Potential applicants for regional soil health LLs	Presentation
20	Mar. 2023	Jump-start the Mission Soil - Cluster event	Belgium	Practitioners, scientists and NGOs	Presentation
21	Mar. 2023	Nati00ns Hungary event	Hungary	Potential applicants for regional soil health LLs	Presentation
22	Mar. 2023	Nati00ns France event	France	Potential applicants for regional soil health LLs	Presentation
23	Apr. 2023	Nati00ns Portugal event	Portugal	Potential applicants for regional soil health LLs	Presentation
24	Apr. 2023	Launch of Soil Manifesto	Belgium	CoP members or future members	Presentation
25	Apr. 2023	COPA-COGECA	Belgium	Farmers, agricooperatives.	Presentation
26	May 2023	Workshop for Schools: discovering soil	Italy	Teachers and Students	Presentation
27	May 2023	Nati00ns Netherlands event	Netherlands	Potential applicants for regional soil health LLs	Presentation
28	May 2023	Jornada Misiones Horizonte Europa: Novedades y Convocatorias 2023	Online	Researchers, scientists, policy makers, agro-industrial SMEs	Presentation
29	May 2023	ERIAFF Annual Conference	Italy	European Regions	Presentation
30	May 2023	Workshop for schools: discovering soil	Italy	Teachers and students	Presentation

31	May 2023	BBIA Spring Event: The power of microbes and the development of the circular bioeconomy	UK	UK innovators, entrepreneurs, policy makers and legislators focused on biotechnology industries.	Presentation
32	May 2023	Workshop for schools: discovering soil	Italy	Soil teachers	Presentation
33	May 2023	Bio's party	Italy	Citizens	Presentation
34	May 2023	2023 EU AgriResearch Conference	Belgium	Policy makers, practitioners, scientists	
35	May 2023	ACR+ General Assembly	Ireland	potential Soil management stakeholders, NGOs, public administrations, practitioners	Presentation
36	Jun. 2023	EU Green Week	Belgium	policymakers, leading environmentalists	Presentation
37	Jun. 2023	NATI00NS webinar: The Living Lab Essential - how to set up a LL	Online	Living Labs	Presentation
38	Jun. 2023	Meeting of the Parliamentary Team for the Development of Family Farms	Poland	Policy Makers	Presentation
39	Aug. 2023	Wageningen Soil Conference	Netherlands	Soil Professionals	Presentation
40	Sep. 2023	Meeting for the EJP Soil National Hub at Vitenparken	Norway	Norwegian agricultural professionals	Presentation
41	Sep. 2023	European Healthy Soils Conference	Switzerland	Industry, agriculture, and the public sector	Presentation
42	Sep. 2023	National Soil Hub meeting	Online	Researchers	Presentation
43	Sep. 2023	OLLD 2023	Spain	Living Labs	Poster Exhibition Communication Materials at partner's exhibition stand
44	Oct. 2023	2023 Earth System Governance	Netherlands	Researchers & NGO's	Presentation
45	Nov. 2023	Ecomondo 2023	Italy	Policy makers, industry, other Horizon Soil Mission projects	Presentation
46	Nov. 2023	European Soil Week	Spain	Farmers, foresters, policy makers, scientist, SMEs, other practitioners	Presentations, Panel discussion, Posters Communication Materials
47	Nov. 2023	Teaching elements for teaching soil	Italy	Teachers	Presentation
48	Nov. 2023	Advanced Training course on science-based advice for policy in agriculture and environment	Belgium	Researchers, scientists, policy makers, CSOs	Networking

49	Jan. 2024	Smart Soils: Smart Specialisation meets EU Soil Mission	Online	Researchers and Academics, Industry Representnvh@foodbiocluster.dkatives, EU Policy Makers and Officials.	Presentation
50	Jan. 2024	Webinar organized by NCP4Missions	Online	Policy Makers	Presentation
51	Feb. 2024	International Agricultural Show (Salon international de l'agriculture)	France	Stakeholders working in the agricultural sector and curious citizens	Poster
52	Feb. 2024	EJP SOIL National Projekt Workshop	Hungary	Farmers, foresters, policy makers, scientist, SMEs, other practitioners	Networking
53	Mar. 2024	KORN2024	Norway	Research and Academia	Networking
54	Mar. 2024	HuMUS Webinar: Soil Health Training	Online	Education Professionals	Presentation
55	May 2024	IUSS	Italy	Policy makers, stakeholders, institutions, and associations	Presentation and PREPSOIL session
56	Jun. 2024	NBSOIL Academy Launch Webinar	Online	Soil Advisors	Presentation
57	Jul. 2024	4th TERRAenVISION Conference	Spain	Scientists and enthusiasts on climate mitigation, sustainable cities and agriculture and a circular economy	Workshop
58	Aug. 2024	European Society for Agronomy Conference	France	Experts in agronomy	Poster
59	Sep. 2024	LANDSCAPE 2024 Agroecosystems in Transformation: Visions, Technologies and Actors	France	Agroecosystems international experts	PREPSOIL Session
60	Sep. 2024	Open Living Lab Days (OLLD) 2024	Romania	LLs & LH professionals, public officials, corporate leaders, entrepreneurs, academics, and innovators	Communication Materials
61	Oct. 2024	Anmeldung für den Experten-Workshop "Synergien nutzen – Bodenmission umsetzen"	Germany	Soil actors from science and practice	Presentation
62	Oct. 2024	4th EUSO Stakeholders forum	Online	Policy makers and scientists to local actors, civil society representatives and citizens.	Presentation
63	Nov. 2024	Ecomondo	Italy	Education Professionals and industry	Presentation
64	Nov. 2024	Mission Soil Week, session Healthy soils for healthy communities	Belgium	Researchers, policymakers, practitioners, farmers, and other key stakeholders dedicated to improving soil health	Presentation and Communication Materials
65	Nov. 2024	Dehesa Days Workshop	Spain	Local authorities and private organizations	Presentation
66	Dec. 2024	World Soil Day (France)	France	Scientists and Researchers, Farmers and Community Leaders, Students and Youth, International Organizations	Poster

67	Dec. 2024	World Soil Day (Milan)	Italy	Scientists and Researchers, Farmers and Community Leaders, Students and Youth, International Organizations	Presentation
68	Dec. 2024	World Soil Day (Denmark)	Denmark	Scientists and Researchers, Farmers and Community Leaders, Students and Youth, International Organizations	Networking
69	Dec. 2024	Teaching elements for teaching soil	Italy	Teaching Professionals	Presentation
70	Jan. 2025	EU Mission Soil Podcast series Episode #2 - Discover some of the EU Mission Soil funded projects!	Online	Policy Makers, Researchers and Scientists, Agricultural Professionals, Educators and Students, General Public	Presentation
71	Mar. 2025	Soil Literacy Workshop organised by the JRC	Italy	Projects funded under the Soil Mission and stakeholders leading exemplary initiatives on citizen awareness raising	Presentation, networking
72	Mar. 2025	LOESS Esperienze formative ed educative sul suolo	Online	Education Professionals	Presentation
73	Apr. 2025	Bodem Breed, session spatial planning to improve urban soil health	The Netherlands	Advisors, researchers, policymakers, and technician	Presentation
74	Apr. 2025	Joint COMMON FORUM / ALGA Webinar – Integrating Soil Health in Remediation	Online	Professionals involved in the intersection of soil health and environmental remediation	Presentation
75	Jun. 2025	AquaConSoil, session spatial planning to improve urban soil health	Belgium	Scientists and Researchers, Policy Makers, industry and Early Career Professionals:	Panel discussion
76	Jun. 2025	VI National Field Days Bratoszewice 2025	Poland	Farmers and Agricultural Producers, Government Officials and Policy Makers, Young Farmers, Industry Professionals	Presentation

Table 14: PREPSOIL presence at third-party events from M1-36

KPI's, data and analysis

PREPSOIL achieved all the KPIs, surpassing the expected number of posters and flyers to be designed, as well as the project presence at third party events.

Lessons learned and final perspectives

PREPSOIL was able to have an active role in events spread away in over 10 different countries, plus the online events where PREPSOIL outreach went beyond Europe, through presentation but also through panel discussions and other networking activities, to not only promote project activities but also collect additional inputs that contribute to the overall PREPSOIL workplan.

3.9 Website and Zenodo

WP	Task	Main Responsible	Contributing partners
WP1 and WP3	T1.1	TrustIT	AU

KPI	Deadline	Status
500 avg. downloads per individual resource in Zenodo	M36	In progress
Total visitors 15,000 on website	M36	Done
Sessions per month 3,000 on website	M36	Done

Work and achievements

The **PREPSOIL website** is an essential platform for the project, since it showcases PREPSOIL objectives, results, and impact to stakeholders and the public. It served as a central hub for disseminating project updates, publications, and collaboration opportunities.

The whole prepsoil.eu website has been optimised since its launch by following SEO and technical best practices to increase its relevance and attract organic traffic; along with a continuous collaboration with communication efforts undertaken by WP1 via social media and newsletters.

ZENODO offers free and long-term storage of digital research outputs, which is especially useful for publicly funded projects needing to guarantee long-term preservation of their outputs. This enhances the visibility and reusability of PREPSOIL research outputs. A ZENODO icon is available at the bottom of PREPSOIL website, next to the PREPSOIL social media icons, to improve its findability. To add, the “Outputs” section on PREPSOIL website lists materials that are available on ZENODO, representing another smooth way for the user to access materials.

Image 5: PREPSOIL Space on ZENODO (left) and Output area on PREPSOIL website (right)

KPI's, data and analysis

As detailed in Table 14 below, PREPSOIL reached its expected KPIs concerning website visitors and sessions.

Date Range 01/07/22 - 27/05/25	Tracked in Google Analytics	Estimated value	Target	Achieved?
Visitors	22,904	133,587	15,000	YES
Sessions	40,822	238,094 = 6,802/mo	3,000/mo	YES
Views to the Knowledge Hub	5,213	30,405	10,000	YES

Table 15: Summary of Google Analytics values for the period 01/07/22 - 27/05/25 - KH launched 30/06/23

In Table 14 it is indicated the results “tracked in Google Analytics”, as well as an additional column focused on “Estimated Value”, which is a result higher compared to the one listed in Google Analytics. The prepsoil.eu website implements a transparent cookie consent mechanism in full alignment with GDPR and the EU Cookie Law. This rigorous privacy policy results in Google Analytics significantly underreporting statistics, as users often decline cookies when presented with a transparent, non-manipulative choice.

Image 6: PREPSOIL Cookie Message in PREPSOIL Website

To more accurately gauge visitor numbers and session data for the prepsoil.eu website, we have maintained completely anonymised and aggregated records of cookie acceptance rates. As observed in the period up to 28th May 2025, only ~17% of website users accepted analytics cookies (24,640/143,705). This relative acceptance rate value is adopted as a proxy value to estimate the real number of visitors and sessions against the data reported in Google Analytics for the current project’s lifetime (1/07/22 - 28/05/25).

Figure 8: Statistics for the cookie popup banner

In addition to the above, a dedicated paid advertising campaign via Google Ads was launched in March 2025 until the end of the project, to additionally boost traffic to the Knowledge Hub. The campaign ran on a budget of €1,700.00, targeting general English-speaking users in EU and Norway along with the top 3 main localisations by number of resources in the Knowledge Hub: French, Italian and Spanish.

Image 7: LinkedIn with paid advertising campaign

Concerning PREPSOIL ZENODO, the account had available a total of 21 materials, from project public/approved deliverables and presentations done at meetings and third-party events, with an average of 146 downloads and 194 views. While downloads may currently be modest, the platform's strength lies in its role as a trusted, persistent repository, where all the materials will be available in the long run. PREPSOIL materials were uploaded on ZENODO in the latest months, meaning that the number of downloads will increase next month and be closer to the KPI of an average 500 downloads per individual resource.

Lessons learned and final perspectives

The overall success of PREPSOIL website, as already referred, is due to the following SEO and technical best practices to increase its relevance and attract organic traffic; along with a continuous collaboration with communication efforts undertaken by WP1 via social media and newsletters. The Google Ads campaigns implemented ensure that PREPSOIL results reached higher levels of visibility.

As mentioned, ZENODO is a vital open-access platform that empowers researchers to share, preserve, and give visibility to their work—regardless of discipline, funding status, or institutional affiliation - since it embodies the principles of Open Science, offering a free, reliable, and FAIR-compliant repository for all research outputs.

As a lesson learned, PREPSOIL should increase the usage of its ZENODO space, that is, all deliverables, presentations at PREPSOIL and third-party events, communication materials (flyers, posters, booklet etc) to make it uniquely available on ZENODO. This will centralise all PREPSOIL outputs in one single space and improve the overall findability of PREPSOIL results.

But relying solely on the number of downloads recorded on Zenodo does not provide a complete picture, as it overlooks several important factors, which should be taken into consideration in future projects:

- Zenodo's high-quality PDF viewer likely enables many stakeholders to read documents without downloading them. Thus, the number of downloads alone does not reflect the number of readers.
- Certain materials with lower download figures—such as the CDE-strategies and the Data Management Plan—are primarily of internal relevance. These inevitably and significantly reduce the overall average number of downloads. Conversely, documents such as The PREPSOIL Taxonomy and Self-assessment for Living Labs and Lighthouses in the Mission Soil Context: A Guide for Users have far exceeded the relevant KPI, achieving 579 views and 425 downloads.
- The PREPSOIL community on Zenodo was established only a year after the project commenced. Additionally, it was not until April 2024 that the consortium became aware that deliverables pending approval could still be uploaded to Zenodo. These factors likely contributed to the lower number of downloads observed and represent important lessons to be considered in the planning and execution of future projects.
- In addition, many results published in recent months have not yet had sufficient time to be fully communicated and disseminated, indicating substantial potential for increased visibility and engagement in the near future.

3.10 Peer-reviewed articles

WP	Task	Main Responsible	Contributing partners
WP1 and WP7		AU	INRAE, ZALF,

KPI	Deadline	Status
5 peer-reviewed articles	M36	In progress

Work and achievements

The PREPSOIL consortium partners have made significant efforts to produce results that are valuable not only within academic circles but also in practical, real-world contexts. Innovative approaches such as citizen science, best teaching practices, and tools tailored for Mission Soil Living Labs play a crucial role in advancing soil health, even if they do not always align with traditional scientific publication themes.

Data and analysis

Title	Status	Journal/platform	Peer-reviewed
Citizen Science for Soil Monitoring and Protection	Published	Preprints.org	No
Citizen Science for Soil Monitoring and Protection	Published	Sustainability	Yes
Citizen Science for Soil Monitoring and Protection	Submitted	Journal of Agricultural Engineering	
Why is remote sensing underutilized for soil health monitoring? Bottlenecks and future directions	Rejected	European Journal of Soil Science	
Why is remote sensing underutilized for soil health monitoring? Bottlenecks and future directions	Submitted	Soil Security	
Uncovering Soil Needs: Understanding degradation and ecosystem services across European regions, Ecology and Society	Submitted	Ecology&Society	
Scale matters: Key regional research and innovation needs to support Soil Health Living Labs	In progress		
Communities of practice in Europe for enhancing soil health – stakeholder engagement and mutual learning processes	In progress		

Table 16: Scientific articles produced as a part of PREPSOIL

Lessons learned and final perspectives

Meeting this KPI within the project period has been challenging, as many outputs have only reached maturity in recent months. As leaders of WP1, we are confident that the committed authors of the papers listed above will successfully achieve peer-reviewed publication.

3.11 Ethical Aspects

WP	Task	Main Responsible	Contributing partners
WP1	T1.1	AU	

Regarding data privacy and data management, this deliverable incorporates information from the prepsol.eu website, which employs a transparent cookie consent mechanism fully compliant with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the EU Cookie Law.

Coordination and collaboration among project partners have been conducted primarily through online platforms, thereby reducing the project's environmental footprint.

As communication professionals, it is crucial to translate scientific language into content that is more readily understood by wider audiences. This objective has been central to the communication and dissemination efforts throughout the PREPSOIL project. Building upon that foundation, this deliverable seeks to clarify terminology that may be unfamiliar to non-specialists, ensuring that the content is accessible to all. Once approved, it will be published on the open-access platform Zenodo.

Gender equality, diversity and social and environmental impact is reflected in the graphic design that characterizes PREPSOIL where people of different age, sex, shapes, and colours are represented.

3.12 Summary

WP	Task	Main Responsible	Contributing partners
WP1	T1.1	AU	TrustIT

In an increasingly digital and social media-driven world, it has been genuinely refreshing to host numerous engaging in-person meetings with stakeholders, diverse audiences, and the consortium itself. These face-to-face interactions have proven to be highly impactful. A prime example is the PREPSOIL Final Event in Brussels in May 2025, where—despite limited time and budget—the Consortium prioritised physical attendance to present an impressive array of outputs to interested representatives from across regions and sectors, both within and beyond the EU. The event placed particular emphasis on the KERs, which are introduced in the following section of this report.

Social media platforms continue to evolve at a rapid pace, making it challenging to set long-term targets for a project spanning three years. Therefore, a flexible and adaptive strategy is essential when working with social media. With the right expertise and experience, these platforms remain among the most effective tools for disseminating targeted content.

On social media, LinkedIn once again proved to be a highly effective platform for professional communication, enabling the project to exceed its engagement KPIs. Since the change from Twitter to X and subsequent updates in UX and algorithms, it is no longer possible to obtain the relevant data from this platform. Furthermore, the change in management at X has raised concern spreading in both academia and amongst others of the stakeholders and target audiences. In the science community there has been a noticeable migration from X to other social media like Blue Sky and Mastodon. AU is closely monitoring this trend to determine which social media platform will emerge as the primary channel for future communication in large-scale scientific programmes. However, the strong performance of PREPSOIL’s LinkedIn presence enabled a strategic reallocation of resources away from X, effectively balancing its declining effectiveness with a stronger than expected performance on LinkedIn.

Throughout the project lifetime PREPSOIL has strived and succeeded in establishing enduring platforms for interaction and engagement with a broad range of stakeholders across diverse land uses. A highly prioritised focal point has been the involvement of national authorities, raising their awareness and informing them of the potential policy levers available to enhance soil health. Overall, PREPSOIL has embraced a proactive and collaborative approach to stakeholder engagement with the primary aim of ensuring a genuine alignment between PREPSOIL’s outputs and the requirements of its stakeholders. The effective dissemination of project outcomes to relevant audiences has encouraged their subsequent uptake and implementation, thereby enhancing stakeholder empowerment.

4. EXPLOITATION

WP	Task	Main Responsible	Contributing partners
WP1 and WP7		AU	ACTA, ENoLL, WUR, IUNG, INRAe, LESP, INIA-CSIC, NIBIO, SLU

4.1 Introduction

By the end of 2024, it became evident that the PREPSOIL project had generated such significant output that an extraordinary measure was required. Consequently, the Consortium agreed to assess the potential for a final event. The explicit purpose of this event would be to present the impressive list of KERs to a large group of stakeholders in physical attendance. The European Committee of the Regions kindly offered to host the event, and on the 26th of May 2025, 72 participants representing all stakeholders from across regions and sectors joined the PREPSOIL Final Event. A fully packed programme with presentations, keynote speakers and panel discussions revolving around selected KERs.

Niels Halberg (Aarhus University / PREPSOIL Coordinator) opened the day by reflecting on the project’s origins in 2022, a time when there was no Soil Monitoring Law on the horizon. PREPSOIL initially focused on laying the groundwork by developing tools and creating spaces for interaction and knowledge-sharing, aiming to improve awareness and raise soil literacy across Europe. Now, three years later, PREPSOIL’s output is being actively taken up to support the deployment of the Mission Soil. The project has shifted from raising awareness to enabling practice, providing knowledge, stakeholder engagement tools, and region-specific insights that public authorities, researchers, and civil society actors can use, adapt, and further develop to improve soil health across Europe.

Frida Nilsson, Member of the European Committee of the Regions, emphasized that soil monitoring requires coordinated, “from the ground up” action at local and regional levels to reflect diverse soil realities. In an [Impact Interview](#) she emphasised that the knowledge, the data, and the networks of PREPSOIL is needed to create action. Jelena Vidovic from the DG AGRI Mission Soil Secretariat presented key Mission Soil achievements and reinforced PREPSOIL’s role in accelerating soil health governance across the EU.

Session 1: Enabling Public Authorities to Apply Soil Health Tools

Moderated by Pablo Gómez Grande (INIA-CSIC / PREPSOIL), this session focused on how PREPSOIL’s regional soil needs assessments, coordination tools, and stakeholder dialogues support public authorities in translating soil health objectives into territorial action.

Saskia Keesstra (WUR / PREPSOIL) presented the regional soil needs assessment framework, which several regions and Mirror Groups are already adapting as a decision-support tool. [An Impact Interview with Saskia Keesstra can be found on YouTube here.](#)

Panellists including Pierpaolo Piras (CoR) and Bavo Peeters (DG ENV) emphasized the importance of using this framework, alongside PREPSOIL's capacity-building materials, to equip Member States and regions with actionable, context-sensitive data.

Other panellists, such as Lydie Sombre and Oskars Balodis, stressed that soil literacy tools and engagement formats piloted in PREPSOIL are ready to be reused and scaled within regional administrations and advisory systems – helping bridge the gap between science and governance.

Session 2: Scaling Living Labs and Lighthouses for Regional Impact

Moderated by Saskia Keesstra, this session zoomed in on Living Labs and Lighthouses, PREPSOIL's innovative platforms for soil co-creation, experimentation, and long-term regional learning.

Isabelle Couture and Mar Ylla (ENoLL / PREPSOIL) showcased the project's Living Lab methodology, now being replicated by partners in collaboration with regional authorities.

The panel, which included representatives from IRTA, Pays de la Loire Chamber of Agriculture, DIMITRA, and RISE, demonstrated how these labs are embedding themselves in existing soil governance structures to ensure sustainability beyond PREPSOIL.

Laura Nougues (Deltares / SOILL-Startup) presented how the SOILL and SOILL-Startup initiatives will further exploit PREPSOIL methods by supporting new labs, scaling existing ones, and creating platforms for shared learning and impact evaluation.

Session 3: Civil Society Engagement Tools Ready for Uptake

Moderated by Jennie Barron (SLU / PREPSOIL), this session highlighted ready-to-use tools and strategies co-developed to raise soil literacy and activate citizen involvement.

Christina Lundström, Tove Ortman, and Valeriya Fetisova presented concrete outputs, including tools for soil co-learning, citizen soil ambassador training, and inclusive stakeholder mapping.

Panellists such as Fernando Coelho (Lipor) and Sonia Rodrigues (CURIOSOIL) shared how these engagement methods are already being adopted in ongoing projects, demonstrating clear exploitation of PREPSOIL's outcomes beyond the consortium. [See also the Impact Interview conducted with Sonia Rodrigues here!](#)

Session 4: Sustaining National-Level Capacity Building

Moderated by Niels Halberg, the final session explored how national stakeholders can institutionalize PREPSOIL coordination formats such as Mirror Groups and national soil hubs as permanent stakeholder forums for soil governance.

Flavien Poinçot (ACTA / PREPSOIL) highlighted that several Member States are already interested in embedding these platforms in long-term governance systems.

José Luis Pita-Romero Herrero (INIA-CSIC / PREPSOIL) noted that PREPSOIL's soil monitoring knowledge base is now accessible to support ongoing training and policy development across the EU. All presentations, photos, and session summaries from the PREPSOIL final event are available at prepsoil.eu. All Impact Interviews can be found on the [PREPSOIL YouTube channel](#).

In addition to the substantial efforts dedicated to the Final Event, WP7 has coordinated a structured process aimed at collecting and harmonising information regarding the various exploitation activities undertaken across all work packages. A standardised template was developed and distributed to all Work Package and Task Leaders to capture details of these activities. This was followed by a request to complete a more concise PowerPoint slide, intended to facilitate discussion during the Consortium Meeting held on 27 May in Brussels. The outcome of this process is a consolidated list of KERs, accompanied by descriptions of the actions implemented to support their effective exploitation.

The following section will present the individual KERs, not only by description of the results themselves but also with focus on the actual and/or potential use of the result, a definition of the relevant stakeholders and the potential for collaboration, and finally, a list of other projects, EU entities, national or international organisations who will ensure the potential or continued use of the output.

4.1.2 Fostering the establishment of Mirror Groups

WP	Task	Main Responsible	Contributing partners
WP1	T1.2	ACTA	AU, NIBIO, WUR (main partners, contributing to all actions) ; ZALF, Re-Soil Foundation, SLU (participated to the bilateral meeting with their country); Re-Soil Foundation, SLU, ACR+, CSIC, Deltares, ÖMKI, ENOLL, Fundecyt-PCTEX (participated to T1.2 meeting)

Description

This KER has given an overview of existing Mirror Groups and countries with similar groups as well as an opportunity to clarify what is a Mirror Group and expectations from the Commission. Furthermore, direct interaction with countries to foster the establishment or development of such groups has taken place. As a result of the thorough work, feedback and recommendations to build Mirror Groups are now available to all. These recommendations can potentially lead to the development of several Mirror Groups in Europe. The dynamic has already started and the information from the work is clearly expected.

Supporting open access materials are:

- Written report
- Recording from Final Event 26 May 2025
- Recording from webinar 16 June 2025
- Communication materials from the webinar

All material is available on Zenodo and [PREPSOIL website](#)

Use of result

The Mission Secretariat will use the results to continue the promotion of Mirror Groups and are likely to start a network - or at least a regular discussion between Mirror Group coordinators. Mission Board members will use the results to reflect on their recommendations as the work has already partially been presented to them.

Stakeholders and collaboration

The main targets are stakeholders involved, or likely to be involved in the future, in the establishment and management of Mirror Groups across Europe. They are mainly ministries of the European member states, national agencies as well as the Commission and Mission Board members.

Future projects involving science-to-policy interfaces are expected to have an interest in using the results. Although the specific project is not yet funded, there is a topic in the current call dedicated to science-to-policy interfaces where the selected project would benefit from the PREPSOIL results regarding Mirror Groups.

The result is developed in close collaboration with both the Mission Secretariat and Mission Soil Platform, and both could be ready to take up the productions. The Mission Secretariat is to continue fostering the dynamic, mission implementation platform as Mirror Groups are supposed to be named on their website.

4.1.3 Synthesis of soil needs and drivers of change for different land use types across 19 regions in Europe

WP	Task	Main Responsible	Contributing partners
WP2	T2.1	WUR and ZALF	ZALF, AU, CSIC, SLU, DELTARES

Description

In this deliverable, the in WP2 developed Soil Needs Assessment (SNA) framework was described and how it was used in 20 regions across Europe. The SNA framework effectively analyses regional socio-economic and geo-biophysical interactions shaping soil health. It serves as an interdisciplinary complex systems approach for assessing regional soil health challenges in collaboration with stakeholders. We recommend its use as a foundational step in designing and implementing soil health-related living labs. To include integrating soil health into land use decisions, policies, and economic incentives; promoting multifunctional agriculture; minimizing soil sealing; and managing land abandonment. The systems approach enhances understanding of soil-society interactions, helping design effective, stakeholder-driven responses to improve soil health across Europe.

Supporting open access materials are:

- Synthesizing soil needs and drivers of change across Europe and land use types. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.18174/651649>
- Soil Needs and Drivers of Change Across Europe and Land Use Types - Booklet (Version 1) [Computer software]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10693699>
- Report from Trans-European event on soil needs assessments. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11927835>
- [Soil by Region | Prepsoil](#)

Use of result

The result has high scientific potential and the methodology is interesting to be upscaled to other regions.

Stakeholders and collaboration

The primary stakeholder group is researchers. The information in this deliverable was used in the remainder of the work in PREPSOIL, especially by WP2 for D2.2. The SOLO project also made use of part of the methodology developed to assess the drivers in Land use change and soil degradation.

4.1.4 Regional focussed strategic research and innovation agenda

WP	Task	Main Responsible	Contributing partners
WP2	T2.5	WUR	ZALF, SLU, DELTARES, CSIC

Description

The regionally focused strategic research and innovation agenda (SRIA) has high policy or regulatory potential. Policy recommendation, guidance, awareness raising, advocacy. The type of result is categorised as policy recommendation, guidance, awareness raising, advocacy.

This strategic agenda outlines regional soil health research and innovation needs across Europe, informed by assessments in 21 regions. It supports the development of Soil Health Living Labs (LLs) through co-creation and stakeholder collaboration. Key areas include scientific research, innovation, monitoring, and scaling. Needs vary by land use (agriculture, forestry, urban, mixed) and region. Barriers include funding, policy misalignment, and low soil literacy. Solutions emphasize long-term funding, cross-sector policy coherence, and landscape-level approaches. LLs must integrate diverse actors and tailor solutions to ecological and socio-economic contexts, advancing sustainable soil management to address climate and societal challenges.

The material has been put on the platform of PREPSOIL to be downloaded. Furthermore, several people in the WP2 team are working on transforming this report into a scientific report to be submitted after the deadline of the project.

Supporting open access materials are:

- Regional focused strategic research and innovation agenda: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15205666>
- Specific link to the material on PREPSOIL's Zenodo Community

Use of result

The SRIA can be used for future programming of the Soil Mission and other related Missions. It is useful for running and future LLs and LHs as well as for potential funders on national and European level.

Stakeholders and collaboration

The primary stakeholders of this result are policymakers and authorities. The following projects have been contacted with the purpose of exploring synergies and possibilities for exploitation: The SOLO project, the final part of the EJP SOIL project (already happened, but was exploited there), The Cliefarms project, The REACT4MED project and The SOILL project.

4.1.5 PREPSOIL Knowledge Hub

WP	Task	Main Responsible	Contributing partners
WP3	T3.3	TrustIT	All partners

Description

The [Knowledge Hub](#) is an online catalogue of soil resources hosting almost 300 resources in 13 different languages and in various formats such as documents, videos, webpages, factsheets, audiofiles, infographics and presentations.

Supporting open access materials are:

- [Knowledge Hub | Prepsoil](#)

Use of result

The Knowledge Hub was built to improve access to robust and reliable existing soil resources to raise awareness about soil health. Any user (organization, academic institution or individual) can submit resources allowing them to:

- Boost discoverability of their materials reaching a broad audience of researchers, policymakers, and citizens.
- Increase visibility – because all resources maintain their original hosting (e.g. your institutional library, YouTube channel, Zenodo listings) and directs traffic back to where it is stored.

Stakeholders and collaboration

The Knowledge Hub is designed to serve a variety of national and regional stakeholders from land users, advisors, to teachers/trainers, civil servants and researchers and therefore it welcomes all kinds of “soft” material in many formats and any European language, making it a multi-lingual repository.

During spring 2025, Soilwise and JRC entered into dialogue with PREPSOIL about the Knowledge Hub and to spread awareness about it, it was agreed that PREPSOIL would reach out to all (+50) Mission Soil projects asking them to submit their soil resources to the Knowledge Hub.

4.1.6 PREPSOIL Mobile App

WP	Task	Main Responsible	Contributing partners
WP3	T3.2	TrustIT	All partners

Description

The PREPSOIL Mobile App is a user-friendly, interactive tool that connects citizens and researchers, facilitates data collection, and encourages knowledge sharing on soil conditions and practices. Through the PREPSOIL Mobile App every user can access:

The Knowledge Hub: A multi-lingual online library providing access to over 300 resources on soil

The LL/LH map: An interactive map showcasing Mission Soil Living Labs and Lighthouses

PREPSOIL TV: A catalogue of videos and interviews on soil issues and best practices

In addition, all users have the chance to participate in exciting SOIL QUESTS to become active players in expanding knowledge on soil! Supporting open access materials are:

- <https://apps.apple.com/it/app/prepsoil/id6480288814?l=en-GB>
- <https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=eu.prepsoil.app&hl=en&pli=1>

Use of result

The mobile app gives an opportunity to raise interest in soil health among citizens and provides them with tools to actively contribute

For Researchers: The app enables collaboration with the wider public and provides insights and from diverse regions, valuable for studies, case comparisons, and citizen science initiatives.

For Living Labs & Lighthouses: Use the app as a tool for engagement and as a practical support to your co-creation and experimentation activities around soil stewardship.

For Students and Educators: Gain access to a hands-on, real-world learning tool that can be used in classrooms, fieldwork, and awareness campaigns to foster environmental responsibility and scientific curiosity.

For Policymakers and Public Authorities: Learn how the app can support local engagement, help gather grassroots data to inform policies and promote citizen involvement in sustainability actions.

Stakeholders and collaboration

A webinar was organised for researchers, Living Labs and Lighthouses, students, educators, and policymakers, providing a demonstration of the app's various functionalities. In advance of the event, PREPSOIL partners were encouraged to develop quests within the app to illustrate, in a practical manner, how it can facilitate engagement in citizen science among both the scientific community and civil society. Quests were presented by ACR+, the ReSoil Foundation, and FUNDECYT-PCTEX. Attendees were subsequently invited to create their own soil-related quests using the app.

4.1.7 LL/LH taxonomy, identification and mapping

WP	Task	Main Responsible	Contributing partners
WP4	T4.2 (with input from T4.1)	ENoLL	INRAE, WR, DELTARES, AU, ZALF, ÖMKi, SLU, CSIC, NIBIO, LESP, IUNG, RE-SOIL, F-PCTEX, ACR+, COPA- COGECA

Description

The PREPSOIL Taxonomy for Living Labs (LLs) and Lighthouses (LHs) is a structured framework developed to support the identification, classification, and communication of soil health initiatives in line with the EU Mission Soil criteria. It builds on an extensive literature review, co-creation activities, and conceptual work to provide a common language and structured reference for distinguishing LLs and LHs across various land-use types and stages of maturity. The taxonomy directly feeds into the interactive LL Atlas hosted by PREPSOIL, serving as a foundational tool for mapping, analysis, and strategic planning across the growing European network of soil-focused Living Labs and Lighthouses.

Building on the PREPSOIL Taxonomy, a structured three-level terminology for categorizing Living Labs in the context of soil health has been developed: “Mission Soil Living Labs”, “European Living Labs”, and “Emerging Living Labs.” This terminology, officially endorsed by the European Commission, provides a common reference framework to assess the maturity and strategic alignment of Living Labs with the objectives and criteria outlined in the Mission Soil Implementation Plan. It is expected to endure beyond the PREPSOIL project and serve as a foundational tool for future initiatives under the Mission Soil programme.

To ensure wide accessibility and practical use, all key outputs related to the taxonomy are made openly available. The Taxonomy Deliverable ([D4.1](#)) presents the full methodology, structure, and development process of the taxonomy. The Taxonomy User Guide ([link](#)) provides step-by-step instructions, case examples, and practical tips for practitioners, researchers, and policy actors to apply the taxonomy in real-world contexts. The Interactive Online Tool ([link](#)) allows users to navigate the taxonomy dynamically, explore key characteristics, and apply the classification logic to their own initiatives. The taxonomy is grounded in the Conceptual Framework Report ([link](#)), which situates the role of Living Labs and Lighthouses in improving soil health, providing theoretical and strategic underpinnings. Additionally, the Conceptual Framework Workshop Kit ([link](#)) offers a set of ready-to-use materials to support stakeholder engagement, awareness-raising, and training around the conceptual model and taxonomy.

Use of result

The PREPSOIL Taxonomy is central to supporting a more coordinated and strategic development of soil health Living Labs (LLs) and Lighthouses (LHs) across Europe. As the basis for the PREPSOIL interactive LL Atlas, it enables consistent classification of initiatives, helping map and visualize their scope, focus, and maturity level. This structured approach allows users—such as researchers, local actors, policymakers, and funding bodies—to identify relevant efforts, uncover gaps, and connect with initiatives aligned with their interests or regional contexts.

The taxonomy supports both newcomers and established initiatives by providing a clear framework for assessment and reflection. Emerging LLs and LHs can use the taxonomy to understand where they fit within the broader Mission Soil ecosystem, align more closely with Mission criteria, and better position themselves for participation in future funding calls or networks. For more mature initiatives, it helps benchmark progress and facilitates collaboration by clearly communicating key features and areas of expertise.

Ultimately, the taxonomy enhances clarity, comparability, and connection across the Mission Soil community—laying the groundwork for more effective policy alignment, replication, and scaling of soil health practices.

Stakeholders and collaboration

The development of the taxonomy was carried out in close cooperation with other Mission Soil projects, including SOILL-Startup and NATI00NS, to ensure alignment of language, methodology, and practical use. This collaboration helped validate the taxonomy’s structure and ensured interoperability with tools and resources developed across the Soil Mission community. The taxonomy is also designed to support future uptake within the SOILL FPA, ensuring continuity in mapping, classification, and evaluation efforts as the Mission expands.

Figure 9: Collaboration between PREPSOIL and other Mission Soil projects on the Taxonomy for Living Labs and Lighthouses.

4.1.8 Map of Living Labs and Lighthouses

WP	Task	Main Responsible	Contributing partners
WP4	T4.2	ENoLL	INRAE, WR, DELTARES, SLU, ÖMKI, AU, CSIC, NIBIO, ZALF, LESP, IUNG, RE-SOIL, F-PCTEX, ACR+, COPACOGECA, JRC

Description

The PREPSOIL Map of Living Labs (LLs) and Lighthouses (LHs) is a dynamic, open-access online tool that presents an interactive overview of soil health initiatives across Europe. It highlights LLs and LHs that are active or emerging in their efforts to improve soil health through collaborative, place-based approaches aligned with the principles of the EU Mission 'A Soil Deal for Europe'.

As of the final update, the map features 170 individual sites across various land-use contexts, offering visibility to initiatives and fostering networking, learning, and collaboration. Each mapped initiative is classified using the PREPSOIL LL/LH Taxonomy and contextualized within the criteria laid out in the Soil Mission Implementation Plan.

To ensure broad accessibility and encourage uptake, the PREPSOIL Map is made fully open access via the PREPSOIL website ([see map here](#)). Users can explore the initiatives interactively without restrictions. Supporting materials—such as detailed descriptions of each site, taxonomy information, and contextual documents—are also openly available to provide practical guidance and promote informed use of the platform.

Furthermore, the map is actively integrated into the activities of the SOILL Framework Partnership Agreement (FPA) projects, supporting long-term continuity and increased visibility within the broader Mission Soil ecosystem.

Use of result

The PREPSOIL map is more than a directory—it is an engagement tool designed to support knowledge exchange, identify practice gaps, and strengthen the Mission Soil network. In addition to visualizing LL and LH initiatives, it incorporates an assessment process that evaluates each initiative's alignment with the principles and criteria defined for Mission Soil LLs and LHs.

To this end, a targeted outreach campaign was launched: 133 mapped initiatives were invited to complete a self-assessment, and a broader communication campaign promoted the opportunity across PREPSOIL channels and Mission Soil projects. As a result, 84 total responses were received 53 from previously mapped initiatives, and 31 from new applicants that accounts for 43 new LL/LH sites added to the map.

These assessments provide critical data to understand the maturity and focus areas of current initiatives, identify capacity gaps, and inform the development of support tools and trainings. Initiatives that meet the minimum criteria will be guided through further steps, including deeper evaluations and potential inclusion in capacity-building activities under future projects such as SOILL.

The map and assessment process together form the foundation for a structured, strategic ecosystem of soil health LLs and LHs, enabling both coordination and growth across Europe.

Stakeholders and collaboration

PREPSOIL have closely coordinated with Mission Soil sister projects to ensure compatibility and alignment in the development and use of the map. This includes strategic collaboration with the SOILL Framework Partnership Agreement (FPA) projects, particularly SOILL-Startup. Emphasis has been placed on facilitating the transfer of mapping and assessment data from PREPSOIL to SOILL to support continuity, avoid duplication, and build on existing efforts.

Mapped initiatives and assessment results will feed into the updated SOILL map and evaluation tools, supporting the seamless integration of PREPSOIL outcomes into the next stage of Mission Soil implementation. The assessment data will also help identify where additional support, training, or matchmaking is needed—ensuring that initiatives already engaged through PREPSOIL can be meaningfully supported and expanded under future programs.

Image 8: The Living Labs map on SoilLL's website

4.1.9 Business Model interactive Canvas

WP	Task	Main Responsible	Contributing partners
WP4	T4.3	ENoLL	INRAE, WR, DELTARES, SLU, AU, F-PCTEX, ÖMKI

Description

The PREPSOIL Business Model Canvas (BMC) for Soil Living Labs (LLs) and Lighthouses (LHs) is a strategic and practical tool designed to help soil health initiatives define, refine, and communicate how they create, deliver, and capture value. Developed specifically in response to the needs of LLs and LHs working toward the goals of the Mission Soil Implementation Plan, the PREPSOIL BMC supports long-term stability and funding readiness.

This interactive canvas was co-designed through a participatory, three-phase process—Understand, Co-Design, and Evaluate—ensuring it reflects real-world operational contexts and user needs. The tool includes two overarching components (Mission Soil objectives and land use type) and 14 essential building blocks of a business model. Each element features contextual “spheres of intervention” to guide tailored input from users across land use types (e.g. agriculture, forestry, post-industrial, peri-urban).

To ensure accessibility and promote uptake, all related outputs are fully open access:

- The PREPSOIL Report on LL/LH Business Model Plans (D4.2), available on Zenodo, provides in-depth methodology and background on the canvas development: [Read here](#)
- The Business Model Canvas Guide for Users, also on Zenodo, offers practical, step-by-step instructions for using the canvas: [Access the guide](#)
- The Catalogue of Real-World Business Model Insights, available on the PREPSOIL website, compiles insights categorized by common, soil-specific, and land-use-specific insights: [Browse the catalogue](#)
- An editable working copy of the canvas is available for download to help LLs and LHs apply the tool directly to their context: [Download here](#)
- The online Business Model Training session, co-developed with SOILL-Start-Up and publicly available via the SOILL platform, offers foundational training and recorded content to enhance understanding: [Watch here](#)
- A brief publication on the importance of business models and financial stability for LLs and LHs is currently under development and will also be made openly accessible.

Use of result

The PREPSOIL BMC is designed to serve as a foundational resource for Soil LLs and LHs in developing compelling, coherent business models that can support financial sustainability and increase their impact over time. It helps initiatives clarify their value proposition, and communicate more effectively with funders, policymakers, and collaborators.

The interactive canvas, user guide, and real-world insight catalogue together form a practical package that can be adopted by soil health LLs and LHs across land use types and development

stages. These tools can be actively used in training and capacity-building activities and will support newer initiatives in identifying gaps or refining strategies to attract investment and strengthen long-term resilience.

Stakeholders and collaboration

The PREPSOIL Business Model Canvas was developed in close collaboration with other Mission Soil projects, particularly through consultations with SoilValues, and joint activities with SOILL-Start-Up. Shared training sessions and co-development of content ensured that the canvas reflects both PREPSOIL’s insights and the broader needs identified across the Mission Soil community.

Further collaboration is being explored under the SOILL Framework Partnership Agreement (FPA) to expand the use of the canvas in the next project phase. This includes integrating the BMC into training into capacity-building pathways to support the next wave of Soil LLs and LHs. These partnerships help ensure continuity, scalability, and added value across the Mission Soil landscape.

4.1.10 Toolbox for Soil Living Labs Growth

WP	Task	Main Responsible	Contributing partners
WP4	T4.4	WUR	INRAE, DELTARES, SLU, ENoLL, AU, F-PCTEX, ÖMKI

Description

The Soil Living Lab Growth toolbox has been co-designed, validated, and refined together with existing Living Lab and Lighthouse initiatives to accelerate the adoption, enhance the maturity, and optimise the operation of soil-related Living Lab and Lighthouse initiatives across various land use contexts. It offers a wide range of resources; from reports and online tools to stakeholder-specific websites and topic-focused materials, designed to support the development of initiatives. For more advanced initiatives, the toolbox can also help identify areas needing further attention. Ultimately, its purpose is to foster stronger alignment of Soil Health Living Lab and Lighthouse initiatives with the EU Mission “A Soil Deal for Europe.”

Supporting open access materials are:

- [Link to Toolkit of Resources for Living Lab Acceleration](#)

Use of results

Selection of different resources, which help emerging and existing Soil Health Living Lab and Lighthouse Initiatives to mature faster, while taking specific criteria for the Soil Mission into account. The tool helps initiatives to learn from experiences of previous initiatives.

Stakeholders and collaboration

Stakeholders to this result are existing or emerging Soil Health Living Lab and Lighthouse Initiatives. The resources in the toolbox can be further taken up by the SOILL startup project where resources can be updated, extended and continued to be made public for people who are interested via the SOILL Hub (<https://soill2030.app/>).

4.1.11 Analysis of knowledge base available to monitor soil indicators

WP	Task	Main Responsible	Contributing partners
WP5	T5.1	IUNG	INRAE, LESP, CSIC, AU

Description

The analysis provides an overview of existing research on soil monitoring and the soil health indicators used, as well as an inventory of national experiences (SMSs or initiatives) in monitoring non-agricultural areas. In addition, knowledge gaps are identified and the need for harmonisation in terms of both monitoring schemes, sampling protocols, indicators and their reference values is pointed out.

Supporting open access materials are:

- D5.1 “Analysis of knowledge base available to monitor soil indicators proposed under the Soil Mission” available on Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/13347951>
- D5.1 on the PREPSOIL website: <https://prepsoil.eu/soil-monitoring>

Use of result

The results can be used as a basis for exploring and developing new research directions in the implementation of Mission indicators for soil monitoring; optimising soil evaluation programmes in urban and post-industrial areas (e.g. feeling gaps and involving soil health principle); some results can be used for training purposes.

Stakeholders and collaboration

The main stakeholders are research institutions, policy makers, city and regional administration.

The results may be useful for any projects (Soil Mission and others) focusing on soil management and evaluation in non-agricultural areas (forest, urban, post-industrial). NBSOIL project will use these results.

4.1.12 Assessments of soil monitoring satellite-based EO

WP	Task	Main Responsible	Contributing partners
WP5	T5.2	INRAe	IUNG, LESP, WR, SLU, NIBIO, JRC

Description

Results combine (i) a review of the literature (ii) interviews with leading scientists on some uses of EO (Earth Observation) (landscape heterogeneity, SOC, soil erosion, and Digital Soil Mapping), (iii) surveys on the use of EO in other UE projects, (iv) an inventory of existing data and products linked to European services (CLMS), (v) the current use of EO in the dashboard of the EUSO, (vi) an regional estimation of water erosion using RUSLE model, and (vii) the identification of obstacles to greater use of EO and measures to reduce them.

Supporting open access materials are:

- D5.2 "Technical feasibility in using CLMS satellite-based EO to estimate soil health indicators": <https://zenodo.org/records/13682515>
- Article: "Xie et al. 2025. Why is remote sensing underutilized for soil health monitoring? Bottlenecks and future directions" submitted on 22 April 2025 to European Journal of Soil Science and later to Soil Security

Use of result

The results on the technical feasibility in using CLMS satellite-based EO to estimate soil health indicators can mainly enlighten non-specialists in remote sensing and identify points that specialists need to improve in order to favour interactions with non-specialists. Results also include technical hurdles that need to be overcome and the still considerable potential for development.

Stakeholders and collaboration

Main stakeholders are policy decision-makers and actors interacting with them, scientists, agronomists and extensionists, lecturers and students.

Projects that can use these results include CUP4SOIL (supported by FPCUP) and AI4SoilHealth (supported by HE).

4.1.13 Citizen Science crucial for soil monitoring

WP	Task	Main Responsible	Contributing partners
WP5	T5.3	LESP	WUR, INRAE, DELTARES, ÖMki, JRC

Description

Citizen science refers to the involvement of non-specialist volunteers in scientific research activities, typically under the direction of professional scientists. The PREPSOIL deliverable D5.3: "Feasibility of citizen science engagement for soil monitoring according to soil needs and LLs" provides an in-depth exploration of the role of Citizen Science in enhancing environmental and soil health monitoring. It shows examples and areas of application, describes the benefits, procedures and is a methodological guide for the possible involvement of other amateur researchers in citizen science.

The Citizen Science initiative / project database is a tool that enables better monitoring of soil quality in parallel (or even separately) alongside more conventional methods and EO satellite survey methods.

Supporting open access materials are:

- D5.3 "Feasibility of citizen science engagement for soil monitoring according to soil needs and LLs" on Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/13284100>
- Article "Citizen Science for Soil Monitoring and Protection" published at [Preprints.org](https://preprints.org)
- Article "Citizen Science for Soil Monitoring and Protection" peer reviewed and published at MDPI Sustainability: <https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/17/11/5042>

Use of result

The result shows examples and areas of application, describes the benefits, procedures and is a methodological guide for the possible involvement of other amateur researchers in citizen science. Potential users could be research organizations, governmental and non-governmental organizations.

Stakeholders and collaboration

Mail stakeholders of these results are industry, business partners, research organizations, governmental and non-governmental organizations, universities, interest groups, policymakers, activists.

The project "ECHO – Engaging citizens in soil science, GA No. 101112869" has been approached to explore synergies and support our efforts to exploit the results through joint activities or engagement.

4.1.14 Training needs for monitoring and assessment of soil health

WP	Task	Main Responsible	Contributing partners
WP5	T5.4	INIA-CSIC	INRAE, LESP, IUNG and JRC (EUSO)

Description

This result offers a comprehensive and modular training curriculum on soil health, designed to prepare public authorities, technicians, and policymakers for the challenges posed by the forthcoming Soil Monitoring Law (SML). Developed through a co-creation process involving over 20 Mission Soil projects and multiple European institutions, key training needs have been identified, leading to the creation of a flexible learning pathway. The curriculum combines technical content, best practices, and regulatory developments.

The added value of this result lies in its adaptability, direct alignment with emerging legislation, and its immediate usability as a training tool by Member States, Living Labs, and public bodies.

Supporting open access materials are (upcoming):

- Open-access deliverables summarizing the training proposals in detail
- Internal report: Potential Training Needs for the Implementation and Transposition of the Soil Monitoring Law
- Detailed agenda of the pilot workshop: Workshop on Soil Health Indicators and Current Regulatory Framework
- Public training needs survey
- Recordings of the workshops and all educational materials will be made available as open-access webinars on the PREPSOIL platforms

Use of result

Reference for National Training: The curriculum and materials can serve as a baseline for national or regional authorities to develop or adapt training programs tailored to their institutional priorities and capacities.

Workshop Recording and Dissemination: All workshops will be recorded and published as reusable webinars, with open access to presentations, videos, and case studies via the project platforms.

Support for Public Policy: The modules include real examples of how soil monitoring data can guide agro-environmental policy decisions.

Use by European Projects: The content can be integrated into training programs of projects working on indicators, MRV tools, degraded soils, or agroecological approaches.

Continuous Improvement: The training needs survey may remain open to allow for annual updates of the content based on regulatory and technological developments.

Stakeholders and collaboration

Main stakeholder groups are identified as:

- National and regional ministries and agencies responsible for soil monitoring
- Officials from the European Commission (DG AGRI, DG ENV, JRC)
- Coordinators and members of Living Labs and Horizon projects related to soil health
- Research institutions and universities with continuing education programs on soil, environment, and governance
- Tech companies and providers of digital and remote sensing solutions for MRV

The result has been adopted as a reference by the MRV4SOC and LILAS4SOIL projects, which will actively participate in the training event as speakers. Both initiatives plan to reuse parts of the modules and materials in their own training programs targeting public administrations, confirming the immediate transferability and alignment with other strategic actions under the Mission Soil.

4.1.15 Engagement with Communities of Practice

WP	Task	Main Responsible	Contributing partners
WP6	T6.1	NIBIO	

Description

Production of 80+ videos with engaged groups of farmers, gardeners, forest workers, advisors, researchers and teachers and how they work with practices to enhance soil health – so called Community of Practice groups (CoPs). The CoP's give new insight in how citizens and practitioners work with and learn about soil health across Europe and giving other initiatives inspiration and new knowledge.

Supporting open access materials are:

- 80+ videos on PREPSOIL TV and YouTube, 20 CoPs showcased on website, scientific publication based on the video content under progress

Use of the results

The results can be used to spread knowledge about practices to enhance soil health and can also create networking opportunities between CoPs.

Stakeholders and collaboration

Main stakeholders to the result are practitioners working with agriculture, forestry and gardening, students, researchers, policy-makers.

Collaboration with CURIOSOIL has been explored, as well as upcoming Mission Soil calls for identifying possible living lab participants.

4.1.16 Educational Success Stories

WP	Task	Main Responsible	Contributing partners
WP6	T6.2	SLU	NIBIO, WR, IUNG, COMMPLA (TRUST-IT), F-PCTEX, Re Soil Foundation

Description

The task was to inspire teachers in primary and secondary schools as well as vocational training to work more and innovative with soil issues with their pupils. We wanted to find good examples on soil education in a European context that could be useful for others to learn and get inspiration from.

Open access materials are:

- <https://zenodo.org/records/14620581>

Use of result

The open calls for best teaching practices for healthy soils for teachers from primary and secondary schools sharing best practices and inspirational materials, has a high impact on teachers/educators.

Stakeholders and collaboration

The primary stakeholders are education/training organisations/learners. Each participator in the Task has worked with national actors to reach out to teachers in their country, and the projects LOESS, CURIOSOIL, HuMUS and NBSOIL received invitation to the webinar about best teaching examples.

4.1.17 Synthesis of training needs and co-learning strategies for AKIS in soil health

WP	Task	Main Responsible	Contributing partners
WP6	T6.3	SLU	WUR, AU, IUNG, ZALF, CSIC, INRAE

Description

Task 6.3 pinpointed lack of awareness/knowledge and lack of governance as two hindrances for improved soil health, both across land use types and countries. At EU level, the importance of improving soil health is clearly formulated in the Mission Soil. However, there seems to be a gap between the EU level and the national/regional level. As long as soil health is not considered an urgent question also at national/regional level and not integrated in relevant policies and steering documents, it will consequently not be considered as an important aspect to take into account when it comes to soil management practices in the different land uses. The lack of national/regional clarity on how to integrate the Mission Soil ambition in different land uses in different countries/regions, most likely also affect the willingness and possibilities to participate in competence development measures in soil health relevant topics.

Supporting open access materials:

- Synthesis of training needs and co-learning strategies for AKIS in soil health (<https://zenodo.org/records/15349806>)

Use of the results:

The main goal of the Mission Soil is to lead the transition towards healthy soils by 2030. In order to reach the ambitious goals, set by the mission, people who manage soils will need to do things differently. Hence, new practices need to be developed. In this process, advisors, consultants and other influential key actors will be important mediators of change. But, in order for these key actors to be able to inspire and motivate landowners and land managers (in agricultural, forest and urban soil contexts) to make changes in prevailing soil management practices, it is of utmost importance that they: i) are aware of the EU Mission Soil and ii) have enough knowledge regarding soil management practices that supports a positive development of the soil health.

The report gives valuable insights about soil health awareness among key stakeholders in agricultural, forest and urban land uses.

Stakeholders and collaboration

Each participating country has conducted three online surveys targeting key stakeholders in agricultural, forest and urban land uses (the surveys were done in local languages, but the questions were the same across countries). The partners have also conducted qualitative focus group interviews with farmers and advisors to analyse strengths and weaknesses among two different kinds of learning systems (Communities of Practice) within soil health – one grass-root, self-organised farmer initiative and one public/private extension (programme).

The main stakeholder groups are identified as:

- Researchers
- Policymakers and authorities, international
- Policymakers and authorities, national
- Policymakers, regional or local
- Education/training organisations/learners

Each partner has identified suitable national platforms and/or channels to inform and discuss the results to a wider public, e.g. conferences/seminars, soil days, fact sheets, newsletters etc.

Soil Health Living Lab-funded projects could be interested in the results to 1) better understand the range of soil science knowledge/soil health awareness that might be present within the group, and 2) to get ideas on what kind of soil health related topics that key stakeholders are interested in learning more about in order to integrate soil health perspectives in their daily work.

5. OVERALL ETHICAL ASPECTS

WP	Task	Main Responsible	Contributing partners
WP1	T1.1	AU	ACTA, TrustIT

Since the submission of D8.2 Ethical Advisor Report, WP1 has worked to take the recommendations of the Ethics Advisor into consideration.

With the projects finalising and many results being published, it has been crucial for all partners to work on the transparency and alignment of project goals. To diversify contacts in the consortium, the contact list shared on Microsoft Teams, has been of great use, and has ensured consistent contact even with changes in staff among partners. Corporation among partners has been valuable – especially when planning and executing the Final Event. The Final Event has also further enforced the connections and network across the project’s stakeholders and partners.

Stakeholder management has been a central component of PREPSOIL with ethical considerations playing a key role for the responsible partners. To ensure GDPR compliance, stakeholder mapping and engagement were supported by a dedicated guide, which included a consent form template to assist partners in conducting ethical and transparent engagement activities. Stakeholder data was stored securely on the PREPSOIL SharePoint platform.

The process of writing this deliverable has been led by Aarhus University in its capacity as WP leader. AU proposed the initial structure and overall content of the deliverable, while clearly stating that contributors were encouraged to adapt and revise the structure as appropriate. As WP leader, AU is responsible for the final submission and certain specific components; however, each contributor remains accountable for their individual contributions.

All contributors were invited to provide reflections on Lessons Learned and Final Perspectives, offering an opportunity for both authors and readers to benefit from shared insights and experiences.

6. OVERALL CONCLUSION

WP	Task	Main Responsible	Contributing partners
WP1	T1.1	AU	

Thanks to a dynamic and fruitful cooperation amongst the partners of PREPSOIL to engage relevant stakeholders and to ensure providing high-quality content, we have successfully achieved every significant and obtainable KPI. In addition to the direct interactions with stakeholders as part of PREPSOIL engagement activities, that allowed partners to promote the project and its outputs. This success has been supported by a well-designed, user-friendly, and technically robust website that is both visually appealing and easy to navigate. Our newsletter has harvested an impressive number of followers, filled with relevant articles aimed at the different target audiences. Complementing this is a social media strategy, dynamic and adaptable to an ever-changing digital landscape of communication, with engaging and relevant content.

Aligned with the three Key Impact Pathways, we have compiled an impressive list of KERs. The PREPSOIL project has produced no fewer than 11 tangible KERs. Looking beyond June 2025, we have identified several projects and organisations poised to further exploit these results, including CURIOSOIL, SOILL FPA, SoilValues, NBSOIL, CUP4SOIL, ECHO, MRV4SOC, LILAS4SOIL, Soil Health Living Labs, and others.

Another noteworthy post-project achievement is PREPSOIL’s active presence at numerous events across Europe. Engaging stakeholders in soil health on an international scale is essential to driving local action. By sharing practical knowledge, fostering the development of multi-stakeholder interfaces, and offering a toolbox of easily implementable solutions, PREPSOIL has remained true to its mission.

As Niels Halberg concluded when wrapping up the Final Event, “This event is not an end, but a beginning.” PREPSOIL has laid solid groundwork for the Mission Soil implementation and, crucially, developed tools, methods, and partnerships that are already being exploited across Europe.

From regional soil assessments and civil society engagement to national coordination platforms and Living Labs, PREPSOIL’s legacy is actively transforming soil health policies into practice across policies, territories, and communities.

Place and date:

*Aarhus University, Foulum
 30 June 2025*

DISSEMINATION, COMMUNICATION AND EXPLOITATION OF PREPSOIL RESULTS

Following the Consortium Meeting in Budapest October 2024, WP1 decided to make an updated CDE plan for the remaining of the project period. This document contains the accumulated overview of KPIs that WP1 seek to achieve until M36, which will also be the basis of the final CDE report, D1.3.

This updated CDE plan has been discussed with WP7 on November 26, 2024 and is approved to be the main guideline for the CDE activities. This means that all mentioned statement of intents in previous deliverables and strategies, such as examples of Future plans in D1.2 as well as Tentative KPIs in the Grant Agreement, part B, are considered as inspiration for CDE activities – however not as targets per se. This plan builds on and replaces the document “PREPSOIL deliverables” sent out to all WP leaders August 26, 2024 in order to get one collected overview.

The KPI tracker will be updated according to the following updated list of KPIs.

UPDATED LIST OF KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

KPI'S DEFINED IN D1.1 AND D1.2 - REVIEWED AND CONFIRMED BY WP1 AND WP7 BY M29

For current status: [PREPSOIL KPIs, Events & Publications Tracker 20240927.xlsx](#)

Category	KPI by M36	Deadline
Community	Total of 2,200 social media members	M36
	Twitter: 1,000 followers, 300,000 impressions, 500 tweets	M36
	LinkedIn: 1,200 followers, 50,000 impressions	M36
	Youtube: 80 videos, 100 views per video	M36
	Total community database: 2,000 D1.1: 500 by M12, 1200 by M24, 2000 by M36	M36
Communication material	3 fliers	M36
	3 posters	M36
	2 roll up banners	M36
	30 presentations	M36
	80 videos	M36
	6 press releases	M36
	500 avg. downloads per individual resource in Zenodo (Table 7: Zenodo community will be used to deposit publications, data and software. Measure: avg. dl per indiv. resource)	M36
	5 peer-reviewed articles	M36
1 project branding package with logos, templates, and collaterals available. (D1.1)	M1	
Newsletters	12 newsletters	M36
Presence at third party events	30 presences at third party physical and virtual events	M36
Website	Total visitors 15,000	M36
	Sessions per month 3,000	M36

OBLIGATIONS OF WP1

To facilitate the exploitation of the project results, WP1 will have an increased focus on communication and dissemination of essentials from PREPSOIL deliverables.

With strong focus on selected social media platforms, WP1 will disseminate relevant PREPSOIL outputs, deliverables and popular articles with significant increase in activities.

The target audience will experience a clear intensification in content towards the finalization of the project.

The work of WP1 will follow the scheduled activities listed in the

Weekly DEC activity plan M30-36

- Written coverage/news piece** about every deliverables with link to the deliverable on Zenodo.
- Layout and print** of the deliverables most relevant to PREPSOIL's target audience.
- News piece published** in PREPSOIL's newsletter, social media and website
- Press release** - if relevant - is sent to international and european magazines
- Local and national distribution** of news piece and social media post via communication representatives in all organizations engaged in PREPSOIL.
- Tagging partners in social media posts** with the handles/tags submitted by the communication representatives
- Mission Soil platform newsletter** will receive suggestions from PREPSOIL WP1 to publish the news pieces with the most relevance

OBLIGATIONS OF PARTNERS AND WP LEADERS

- Contact WP1** no later than one month before the submission of your deliverable. If you're not able to join the monthly WP1/WP3 call, please contact Jesper Emborg (je@dca.au.dk), Ida Brems (ib@dca.au.dk) or Rita Meneses (r.meneses@trust-itservices.com)
- Provide information to WP1** on the findings presented in the deliverable.
- Make sure your deliverable is on Zenodo** once approved. This is crucial to the dissemination of your results and of PREPSOIL as a whole.
- Your local communication representative** will receive the news piece for local distribution and - if relevant - translation. He/she will also receive links to the news piece on PREPSOIL's website and social media posts for comments and reactions.

OBLIGATIONS OF COMMUNICATION REPRESENTATIVES IN ENGAGED ORGANIZATIONS

- Distribution of news pieces:** Publish news pieces in local newsletter and website or send as press releases to local or national magazines published in English
- Translation of news pieces:** If a news piece pertains to local test results or researchers, the news piece should be translated and distributed in the relevant local or national channels and platforms.
- Social media activity:** Comment, share or like the PREPSOIL posts on social media with your organization account. You will receive an email and your organization will be tagged when a new PREPSOIL post is out.

Appendix 03, List of Task 6.1 videos

ACR+	All (general soil focus)	ConcerTo Methodology (Région Pays de la Loire, France)	CoP	Héloïse Even, programme manager for biowaste, biomass an https://youtu.be/... Published on PREPSOIL TV
ACR+	All (general soil focus)	La Fresque du sol – The soil collage (Région Pays de la Loire, France)	Soil advocate	Héloïse Even, programme manager for biowaste, biomass an https://youtu.be/... Published on PREPSOIL TV
ACR+	Agricultural/horticultural	Exploring Peasant Agroecology with La via Campesina (Belgium)	Soil advocate/ short r	In this video, Eliaz Moreau, Land Policy Officer at the EU https://youtu.be/... Under review
ARC+	Urban	Community-Led Soil Unsealing in Amsterdam-West (Netherlands)	CoP	This video documents the transformation of an abando https://youtu.be/... Under review
AU	Agricultural	Praktisk økologi. An example of a community of Practice (Denmark)	Cop	Interview with Michael Elke, head of Landsforeningen Prakti https://youtu.be/... Published on PREPSOIL TV, not described as CoP
AU	Agricultural	Smedegården Organic farming (Denmark)	CoP	Interview with organic farmer Leif Hougaard, who focus https://youtu.be/... Published on youtube, not on PREPSOIL TV
AU	Agricultural/Forestry	Permaculture Myrhis (Denmark)	CoP	Interview with farmer Karoline Nolso Aaen, who has an https://youtu.be/... Approved by editorial board, can be made public
AU	Agricultural/horticultural	Climate Plants (Klimaplanter, Denmark)	CoP	Interview with Magnus Buch, who runs a sustainable pl https://youtu.be/... Published on youtube but not on Youtube
AU	Agricultural/horticultural	Interview with Dieter Pansegrau about the Wurzelhof (Germany)	CoP	The Wurzelhof is part of the community-supported agri https://youtu.be/... Under review
AU	Natural	Working with soils in natural areas (Austria)	CoP	The network Landschaftspflegeverein Thermenlinie-Wi https://youtu.be/... Waiting for release form, review finished
AU	Agricultural/Forestry	Integrated organic livestock-agroforest system (Cerrado, Brazil)	CoP/Short document	The productivity and economic performance of a 1.1 he https://youtu.be/... Published on PREPSOIL TV
AU	Agricultural	Conservation Agriculture (Denmark)	CoP/Soil advocate	Interview with farmer Knud Bay-Smidt, who has 240 he https://youtu.be/... On Youtube
AU	Agricultural	Ulvedal Organic farming (Denmark)	CoP/Soil advocate	Interview with Christian Hjorth, an organic farmer who p https://youtu.be/... On Youtube
AU	Agricultural/horticultural	Interview with Jochen Höft: Promoting Soil Health in Organic Farming (G	CoP/Soil advocate	Jochen Höft manages a small organic farm with 1.5 he https://youtu.be/... On Youtube
ENOLL	Agricultural	OptiFarm: Pioneering Sustainable Agriculture	Lighthouse	Let's explore the innovative OptiFarm project at Inagro, West https://youtu.be/... On PREPSOIL TV
ENOLL	Agricultural	Agroforestry Lighthouse: Inagro (West Flanders, Belgium)	Lighthouse	Inagro conducts practice-oriented research aimed at su https://youtu.be/... On Youtube
ENOLL	Agricultural	Discovery Center Living Lab (Hungary)	Living lab	In this video, Dora Sztatényi, Living Lab Manager at Discover https://youtu.be/... On Youtube but not on PREPSOIL TV
ENOLL	Agricultural	Coventry University	Living lab	This video showcases the inspiring efforts of Coventry's Urba https://youtu.be/... On PREPSOIL TV
ENOLL	Forest	Blue! Advancing EU projects (Landsberg am Lech, Germany)	Living lab	In this video, Teresa Luber, a Senior Project Manager at Blue https://youtu.be/... On PREPSOIL TV
F-PCTEX	Agricultural/horticultural	Adolfo Chauton – Landscape, Ecology and Gender Association (Spain)	CoP	Interview with Adolfo Chautón, from Asociación Paisaje, Eco https://youtu.be/... Published on PREPSOIL TV
F-PCTEX	All (general soil focus)	Francisca Palacios - Vocational Training Teacher (Spain)	CoP	Francisca Palacios Sosa is an agroecology vocational traine https://youtu.be/... Published on PREPSOIL TV
F-PCTEX	Forest/Agricultural	Francisco Piris - Farmer from Huertas del Abrilongo (Spain)	CoP	Interview with Francisco Javier Piris, farmer at Huertas del Al https://youtu.be/... Published on PREPSOIL TV
F-PCTEX	Agricultural	SEMBRANDO AGUA (Spain)	CoP	SEMBRANDO AGUA is an intergenerational team, dedicated t https://youtu.be/... Published on youtube
F-PCTEX	Peri-urban	ACTIYA Cooperative (Spain)	CoP	One of its main objectives is to restore soil health, and consequ https://youtu.be/... improve the quality of crops and animals relevant to each rural activity
F-PCTEX	Urban/Horticultural	Urban gardens at "Suerte Saavedra (Spain)"	CoPs	ACTIYA is a community focused on the revitalisation o https://youtu.be/... Under review
inrae	All (general soil focus)	The French soil quality monitoring network (Castellet-lès-Sausses, France)	CoP/Soil advocate	This video documents the Urban Gardens initiative in Suerte https://youtu.be/... Published on PREPSOIL TV
inrae	All (general soil focus)	The place of soil in French law (Philippe Billet)	Soil advocate	Since 2000, the RMQS – French soil quality monitoring netw https://youtu.be/... Published on youtube but not on PREPSOIL TV!
inrae	Agricultural	Soil conservation agriculture (Toulouse, France)	CoP	Claudy Jolivet, a research engineer at INRAE's Info&Sols research unit in Orléans, is in charge of the RMQS network and presents its missio
inrae	Agricultural	Advisers to preserve the soil (Uchaux, France)	CoP	Philippe Billet is professor of public law at the Faculty of Law https://youtu.be/... On youtube but on wrong section on PREPSOIL TV
inrae	Urban/Peri-Urban	Scientific interdisciplinarity at the service of Greater Paris farmland (Pari	CoP	Lionel Alletto is Research Director in French National Institut https://youtu.be/... On PREPSOIL TV
inrae	Urban/Peri-Urban	Metropolises and countryside, a win-win territorial dynamic (Paris, Franc	Living lab	The Chambers of Agriculture support farmers through resear https://youtu.be/... Published on youtube but not on PREPSOIL TV!
inrae	All (general soil focus)	The need for soil biodiversity (Paris, French Senate, December 2023)	Soil advocate	André Bernard is President of the Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur Regional Chamber of Agriculture. The video 'Advisers to preserve the soil' pr
inrae	All (general soil focus)	The soil collage (France)	Soil advocate	In 2013, around fifteen research laboratories came tog https://youtu.be/... On Youtube
inrae	All (general soil focus)	I DISCOVERED A NEW SCIENCE!!	Soil ambassador vide	VivAgrilab is a Living Lab initiative, a collaborative pla https://youtu.be/... Under review
NBIO	Agricultural	Field scale composting (Enebakk, Norway)	CoP	Lionel Ranjard is Director of Agroecology Research at I https://youtu.be/... Under review
NBIO	Urban/Horticultural	Urban Capjon / Økern Portal Rooftop garden in Oslo, Norway	Cop	Antoine Pierart is coordinator of the soil theme at the French https://youtu.be/... On youtube but not on PREPSOIL TV
NBIO	Urban/Horticultural	Måina Joner at Skyvedsøen hagelag in Oslo, Norway	Cop	Antoine Pierart is also national coordinator of the Soil colla https://youtu.be/... ge describes the objectives and structure of the Soil colla
NBIO	Agricultural	Catch crops (Enebakk, Norway)	CoP	It's there, beneath our feet, every day. We trample it with https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=SokOznGTNY8
NBIO	Agricultural	The Magic Factory (Vestfold, Norway)	Cop	Interview with Anna Katarina Berg from the Norwegian Agric https://youtu.be/... Published on youtube and on PREPSOIL TV
NBIO	Agricultural/Forestry	Lunds gård: Alley cropping in Sweden	CoP	ØKERN PORTAL ROOFTOP https://youtu.be/... On homepage but no description as CoP under COP section
NBIO	Agricultural	Regenerative agriculture field day at Steinvik farm (Trøndelag, Norway)	CoP	Erik Joner, Head of Department and Research at NIBIO, in c https://youtu.be/... on homepage but no description as CoP under COP section
NBIO	Horticultural/Forest	The food forest at Landås	CoP	Interview with Mare Holthe from Norwegian Agriculture Ext https://youtu.be/... On PREPSOIL TV, and showcased as Cop but no video link. Link to t
NBIO	Agricultural	Allkorn – Landrace seed saving for soil health (Skåne, Sweden)	CoP	The Magic Factory is a biogas plant and fertilizer factory that https://youtu.be/... On PREPSOIL TV, and showcased as Cop but no video link. Link to t
NBIO	Horticultural/Peri-Urban	Holma Folk High School: a tour through a 20 year old forest garden! (SKÉ	CoP	Example farm for agroforestry in Sweden, with alley cropping https://youtu.be/... On PREPSOIL TV. link with showcase Cop: Agroforestry Sweden
NBIO	Agricultural	Perennial crops for soil health 2 (Alnarp, Sweden)	CoP	Trøndelag county has an active community of regenerative f https://youtu.be/... On PREPSOIL TV
NBIO	Agricultural	Village Potager	CoP	The Food Forest in Landås is a commons and a demon https://youtu.be/... On Youtube but not on PREPSOIL TV
NBIO	Agricultural	Landcare Australia	CoP/short document	Allkorn is an organisation consisting of farmers, bakers https://youtu.be/... Under review
NBIO	Agricultural	Perennial crops for soil health 1 (Lund, Sweden)	Cop/Living lab	At Holma Folk High School in Sweden, the community c https://youtu.be/... Under review
NBIO	Agricultural	Svensk kolinlagring: facilitating agroecological farming in Sweden	Cop/Living lab	Perennial plants come with several benefits: less erosi https://youtu.be/... Under review
NBIO	Agricultural	Trøndernes levende lab: Getting started with Soil Living Labs in Norway PREPS	Living lab	A film giving an overview of the soil health in a Nordic perspectiv https://youtu.be/... Under final editing
NBIO	Agricultural/Forest/natural	Soil health north of the arctic circle: a living lab in Finnmark, Norway	Living lab	Andrés Zakar, the former CEO of Fökert, the Capital's compa https://youtu.be/... On Youtube but not on PREPSOIL TV
NBIO	Horticultural/Forest	Stephen Barstow's forest garden (Trondheim, Norway)	Soil advocate/CoP	Andrés Zakar talks about the importance of healthy soils in the cities and https://youtu.be/... the company's own compost depo, just as the importance of con
NBIO	Horticultural	Charles Dowding	Soil ambassador vide	Izolda Mátýás (agricultural engineer in environmental manag https://youtu.be/... On Youtube but not on PREPSOIL TV
NBIO	Agricultural/General soil focus	Soil health in the nordics	Soil ambassador vide	Hundreds of members have joined since the foundation was established https://youtu.be/... in 2015, to be part of this outstanding experience, where children
OMKI	Urban/Horticultural	Composting for the green Budapest (Pünkösüföld Park, Budapest, Hungary)	CoP	Jean-Martin Fortier has dedicated his career to developing, t https://youtu.be/... On Youtube but not on PREPSOIL TV
OMKI	Horticultural	Exploring the way of nature – Foundation for School Gardens (Veresegyháza, H.	CoP	Gyöngyösi Emese, research project leader of ÖMKI Research https://youtu.be/... On Youtube but not on PREPSOIL TV
OMKI	Agricultural/horticultural	Soil health is the foundation of biointensive market gardening (Terény, Hunga	CoP	Citizen science projects or community research projects have lots of advantages, because researchers can collect a lot of data from various
OMKI	Horticultural	Leafmould instead of peat? The sustainable growing media! (Budapest, Hunga	CoP	Produced by ÖMKI – Hungarian Research Institute of Organic Agriculture for the PREPSOIL project (https://prepsoil.eu), financed by the EU
OMKI	Agricultural	To see agriculture as an ecosystem (Pallagvölgyi Organic Garden, Hunga	CoP	The Pallagvölgyi Organic Garden (Pallagvölgyi Biokert) https://youtu.be/... Under review
OMKI	Horticultural	Zsámbok Organic Farmers Club (Zsámbok, Hungary)	CoP	Matthew Hayes (initiator of Zsáboki Biokert Organic Fa https://youtu.be/... Under review
OMKI	Agricultural	The most important aspect is increasing soil literacy (Csoroszllya Farm, !	Soil advocate	Vitália Vig, a recognised soil ecologist shares her thoughts ab https://youtu.be/... On Youtube but not on PREPSOIL TV
RE-Soil	Agricultural	Cascina Felizia: the educational commitment - Re Soil Foundation (Cumiana Pie	Lighthouse	The Hungarian Research Institute of Agriculture (ÖMKI) https://youtu.be/... Under review
Re-soil	Urban/Horticultural	Terra Felix Social Cooperative (Italy)	Cop	Roberto Pons, owner of Cascina Felizia farm, explains the cer https://youtu.be/... Published on youtube but not on PREPSOIL TV!
Re-soil	Forest	Good practices for forest soils - Re Soil Foundation (Piedmont, Italy)	CoP	Carlo Canale, forestry worker, talks about the importance of https://youtu.be/... Published on homepage, not described as CoP
Re-Soil	Agricultural/Forestry	Iside regenerative agro-silvo-pastoral systems (Lombardia, Italy)	CoP	Carlo also describes some of the best practices they have conducted, among them the use of biodegradable oils for machinery and chainsa
Re-Soil	Agricultural	Cascina Felizia: good practices - Re Soil Foundation (Cumiana Piedmont, Italy)	Lighthouse	Iside Farm is a seven-hectare agricultural project dedic https://youtu.be/... On Youtube
Re-Soil	Agricultural	Terzeria farm and livestock enterprise (Calabria, Italy)	Lighthouse	Roberto Pons, owner of the farm Cascina Felizia explains the https://youtu.be/... Published on youtube but not on PREPSOIL TV!
Re-Soil	Agricultural	La Scoccesa Korean Natural Farming (Tuscany, Italy)	Lighthouse	Società Agricola Terzeria s.r.l. is a farm and livestock e https://youtu.be/... On Youtube
SLU	Agricultural	Gropen – increasing soil literacy by digging a hole (Borgeby, Sweden)	CoP/Soil advocate	La Scoccesa, a farm located among the hills of the mur https://youtu.be/... On Youtube
SLU	Forest	Soils in forest management: a lighthouse example in Northern Europe (Västerc	Lighthouse	Welcome to the complex life below ground! Gropen (The Pit) https://youtu.be/... Published on youtube but not on PREPSOIL TV!
SLU	Agricultural	Farming in Balance (Odling i balans - Hacksta gård (Sweden)	Living lab	Joshua Ratcliffe, researcher and research engineer, Departm https://youtu.be/... Published on PREPSOIL TV but not on map